

Acoustic Emission Testing at Elevated Temperatures using Zinc Oxide Thin Film Broadband Sensors

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Thesis is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland for the award of
Doctor of Philosophy

March 2022

Abstract

This research is focused on the detection and location of simulated AE sources in plate-like structures using zinc oxide (ZnO) based thin film sensing devices.

Typically, thin film piezo devices have higher center frequencies from MHz-GHz. To use them for low frequency spectrum (less than 1 MHz) was the main question in this work. It was expected that the sensing devices would become less sensitive with a reduced signal to noise ratio when operate off- the- resonance. The signal conditioning hardware was built in-house to achieve reasonably improve SNR of the acquired data.

For the deposition of zinc oxide thin films at micro-scale, a physical vapour deposition method was used. Thin films were sputtered on aluminium foil substrate using DC magnetron sputtering system under the optimised conditions. The film structures and crystal orientations were investigated using X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis and scanning electron microscope (SEM).

To validate the performance of the bespoke thin film devices, the linear and triangulation AE source detections and localisation were performed. For simulated AE sources, both the pencil lead break and ball drop methods were used. For benchmark purposes, the performance of commercial AE sensors (UT-1000 from Physical Acoustic) was examined against the bespoke sensing devices.

Data acquired using thin film devices for linear source location were suggested dominated anti-symmetric Lamb wave mode (A_0), using the velocity of the A_0 wave mode the known and assessed source location was found in good commitment. For triangulation source location, the acquired data from thin film devices suggested a mean distance vector error of 0.013 m, the error value was found about 0.01 m smaller relative to the commercial AE sensing devices. The lower error in measurements with thin film sensors is possibly due to the difference in piezoelectric properties between the thin film and bulk PZT elements.

Thin film devices were examined for detecting simulated AE sources at elevated temperatures up to 300 °C, the results demonstrated that the sensing competence of the bespoke sensors with anti-symmetric zero-order Lamb wave mode (A_0). It was found that the velocity of the mode decreased with the increment in temperature, in other words, the mode arrived later time as the

temperature increased. The amplitude of the acquired signals deteriorated gradually with an increase in temperature. Two possible reasons for this trend would be (i) poor acoustic coupling and designed assembly deterioration (ii) the disparity in the coefficients of thermal expansions (CTEs) of the ZnO thin film and the test specimen.

For future work, it is recommended to implement research outcomes in a commercial environment. This opportunity gives more confidence about the performance of developed AE systems with integration to bespoke thin film AE sensors and various data analysis approaches. Also, to utilise the flexibility feature of the thin film AE sensors, it will be useful to examine test geometries other than the plate, such as pipes and pressure vessels, which were not covered in the scope of this feasibility work.

Declaration

I hereby declare that the thesis, entitled “Acoustic Emission Testing at Elevated Temperatures using Zinc Oxide Thin Film Broadband Sensors”, submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy, represent my own work and has not been previously submitted to this or any other institution for any degree, diploma, or other qualification.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank Dr. David Hutson, my director of studies for giving me the opportunity to undertake PhD studies under his supervision, and I am very grateful for his guidance, mentoring, help and support throughout all the years. Also, I would like to thank Prof. Des Gibson, Director of the Institute of Thin film, Sensing and Imaging UWS for his continuous encouragement and support, Prof. Katherine Kirk for helping me out by giving me her valuable support at different stages of this work, Gerry O'Hare providing technical help and support for the experiments, Tom Caddell providing his support for IT support, Andy Bunyan and Dr Liz Porteous for depositing and characterizing the thin films which I have used throughout the years of my research program.

I will forever be grateful to my parents, Sabir Ali Ghouri and Farzana Sabir; my wife, Misbah Ghouri; my brother, Saad Ali Ghouri; and my friends whose support and encouragement have made this thesis possible.

The ultimate gratitude goes to ALLAH Almighty, for His sustaining grace, love, provision, and safety. All wisdom comes from Him.

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Acoustic emission (AE) for structural health monitoring (SHM)

The materials at excessive load generate audible sound which is obvious behaviour. The noise of cracking from wood in mineshafths, the fracture in fibre structure, delamination in composites, fault slip, and the cracking in concrete are all examples of this phenomenon. The occurrence of vibrations inside the material during high load conditions is associated with Acoustic emission (AE). The instant release of strain energy disturbed the microstructure behaviour of the specimen and produced these vibrations resulting in the occurrence of transient elastic waves [1].

Acoustic emissions sources within the material can lead to acoustic vibrations within the sample under test. These vibrations can then be detected by using piezoelectric sensors. The signal conditioning process is applied to the data from each sensing node, the acquired data can use for further meaningful interpretations.

The acoustic emission method of structural health monitoring (SHM) can help to detect and localize the sources of emissions. This method of SHM is to a certain degree different from other methods. Some of the major variances as mentioned in [2] are as follows:

AE based SHM	Other SHM methods
Sense defects growth	defects associated with the shape of the specimen
Require pressure	No stress required
Subtle to material	Less sensitive to material
No geometry subtlety	More geometry oriented
Admittance required only at sensors	A bigger area of inspection required
Main problem noise-related	Main problem: geometry related

Table 1.1 Comparison of AE technique to other SHM methods

When performing SHM, it is wise to use the combination of techniques for detailed analysis of the specimen deterioration. Often when using AE technique, the method is coupled with other non-destructive testing methods. When used in combination the AE method is used for source detection and localization whereas the other method uses for characterising the sources of emissions.

AE method has been applied effectively in a broad variety of materials including metals, concrete, composites, wood, and rock. The technique is applied for the routine testing of pressure vessels, aerospace structures, rotating machinery, pipes, weld analysis and corrosion [6].

The start of AE as it is recognized nowadays is a representation of the research work carried out in the 1950s by German scientists [1]. The research work was carried out first time systematically to study the behaviour of the different noises that are generated during material deformation. The scientist in this research also discovered the Kaiser effect, the phenomenon that defines the shape of AE in a material subject to repetitive cycles of mechanical stress [1].

In 1954 the initial investigation was started in the United States on material engineering applications of AE [1]. In this work, the research scientists found two diverse types of AE namely continuous and burst emissions.

In 1958 important research on the AE phenomenon was also started in France. The research work [1] was published in which the source of emissions through mild steel deformation was investigated. On the foundation of observed theoretical and experimental research few of them mentioned here, this method of SHM has grown attention in the industry from the early 1960s [1].

In several ways, the implementation of AE is not trivial. Advanced systems for monitoring acoustic emissions are not very cost-effective and often required skilled technicians for implementation even for a small-time duration. Practically it is not possible to couple the AE sensors permanently to the test specimens and the coupling of AE sensors is not trivial for specimens with complex geometries. Due to temperature restrictions monitoring of pressure vessels and steam pipes at regular intervals is another challenge with an existing AE system [3]. This restricts the implementation of AE for structural health monitoring for complex geometries which are subject to gain easy access with limits on space and weight [4].

Produce thin film sensing devices using a thin layer of piezoelectric material of a few microns thickness attainment more attention to overcome the above-mentioned issues. Thin films can be deposited on a range of substrates consist of metal, ceramics, silicon, glass, and metal foils for the development of miniaturised AE sensing devices for SHM. Metal oxide such as zinc oxide (ZnO) and aluminium nitride (AlN) based thin film sensing devices can be used for high temperature testing [5].

1.2 Aims and objectives of the research

The main aim of this study is to design and develop thin film AE sensors and use them to detect and locate AE sources after further post-processing of the acquired data. The developed thin film sensors can be used as a standalone sensing device. Due to high Curie temperature limits for metal oxide, these sensors can easily be used for high temperature testing.

The main objectives of the research are mentioned below:

- Design and develop metal oxide (ZnO) thin film sensors and use them for acoustic emission testing as a proof of concept.
- Design and develop instrumentation for AE system
- Examine the sensing ability of the bespoke thin film sensors and benchmark them against commercial AE sensing devices.
- High temperature testing using thin film sensors for AE source detection and localization.

1.3 Thesis structure

This thesis is organised in the following way:

In Chapter 2, a literature review and background study for SHM was conducted with the focus on acoustic emission (AE) method with the advantages of AE technique over other techniques were included. Data analysis approaches were discussed in detail. Contemporary AE sensors made of piezoelectric materials were discussed, different new approaches in the field of sensor design engineering with the focus on thin film technology were presented.

The research work was predominantly focused on the detection of AE signals using thin film devices which leads off the resonance performance for the sensors and ultimately low signal to

noise ratio for the acquired data. To improve the detection ability at low frequency regimes, this work included the design and development of signal conditioning hardware and logic trigger acquisition for the AE system. The conditioning block would help to amplify the acquired data with a gain of ~ 55 dB and the bandpass filter gives 0.6 MHz wide band width. Chapter 3 covered designing and development aspects of electronic circuits and software based logical triggers. The trigger mechanism was discussed in detail including logic diagrams and a programmable approach.

Chapter 4 includes the design methodology of thin film AE sensors. The methods of thin film deposition and characterization were discussed in detail to achieve a good quality of the film which is very crucial for AE sensing devices. The electrical properties were characterized for in-house developed thin film AE sensors and benchmark with commercial AE sensors UT-1000. Details of experiments conducted in the lab using in-house developed thin film AE sensors and commercial AE sensors to detect and locate simulated AE sources in linear and triangulation fashions were discussed.

Chapter 5 included high temperature acoustic emission testing using in-house developed thin film AE sensors. The study of post-annealing treatment of thin films was explained in detail from 100 to 500°C. For high temperature sensing probes, design and characterisation were discussed. The chapter included details about the high temperature AE testing conducted in the lab environment and analysis of raw AE data for source location.

The conclusions are found in Chapter 6. The chapter included a summary of the work carried out in each chapter of this research work. Future work discusses the advancements for thin films AE sensors fabrication, discussion about the possible advancement for instrumentation use for AE systems. Furthermore, the chapter included new approaches for the evaluation of AE data. All necessary programming codes are included in Appendix A. A publication arising from this research work is found in Appendix B and all data sheets included in Appendix C.

1.4 Contribution of this thesis

The research work in this thesis is presented as a proof of concept and several research aspects are presented as feasibility work which will now be described in this section. During this project, zinc oxide-based thin film sensors were employed for acoustic emission testing. The thickness of the active element (in micron scale) would allow resonance frequency greater than

50 MHz and use them for AE sources detection was the real question regarding their sensitivity. To improve the sensitivity and signal to noise ratio of the acquired data, the signal conditioning hardware was designed and developed which is described in detail in Chapter 3. Also, the proof-of-concept software based logical trigger was introduced for recording the AE propagating signals with minimum attenuation. For this purpose, Arduino internal development environment was used which is an open-source tool.

In this work, the deposition of ZnO thin film was another challenge. During this process, I have worked alongside many colleagues in the institute of thin films, sensors, and imaging (TFSI) at the University of the West of Scotland. I would like to thank them all for their regular help and contribution in this project for the deposition and characterisation of the thin film elements. This was an important part of the project because the development of good quality of the thin film was necessary to behave them as a piezoelectric device. The process and parameters selected for thin film deposition are included in Chapter 4, the chapter also included step-by-step design stages of the thin film based bespoke sensing devices.

Another research contribution of this work was to benchmark bespoke thin film sensors with commercially available AE sensing devices. To validate the performance of the thin film sensors, the tests were conducted using metal plate structures in linear and triangulation fashion for source detection and location. For the simulation of AE source ball drop and lead break, methods were used, detail of experiments is discussed in Chapter 4.

The project also covers the high temperature AE testing using the thin film sensing devices as a proof of concept, the detail is covered in Chapter 5. The chapter also included post-annealing treatment of thin film elements, development of high temperature sensing devices and their characterisation. It was found that the sensing device assembly withstands up to 300 °C and is capable to detect AE events.

1.5 References

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CHAPTER 2

Background and literature review

2.1 Introduction

Structural health monitoring (SHM) received considerable attention in various fields of engineering and a good amount of research work has already been done in this area of interest. Different authors define the term SHM in various ways. In literature [1] SHM is defined as a system for continuous and timely examination for the sample under test so that assessment measures can be taken for required actions as per requirement. In literature [2] SHM is used to test sample deterioration and identify its possible life span. In literature [3] SHM is used to examine the geometries in a timely fashion using an array of sensors, further numerical post-processing of the acquired data was carried out for damage detection.

This thesis is focused on the AE method of SHM. The method is considered as a passive, receptive technique analysing the ultrasound pulses emitted by a defect right in the moment of its occurrence. These sound signals transmit through the geometry as guided waves and are acquired by the array of sensing devices. Damage detection is therefore reliant on damage progression or interaction. This implies that AE is not a non-destructive technique.

2.2 Acoustic emission technique

Acoustic emission occurred when localized sources within the material under stress conditions give rapid energy release which promotes the propagation of transient mechanical waves [4]. In engineering materials, AE source occurred due to cracks initiation, elasticity, and debonding. In this technique, AE sensors are used to record elastic waves produced in a structure under stress conditions. The sensors coupled to the specimen sense elastic waves, convert mechanical vibrations into volts and data acquired by acquisition system. The recorded signals are used to extract meaningful information. An illustration of acoustic emission technique is shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1 Illustration of acoustic emission system

Acoustic emission phenomena occurred in a variety of materials some of them are listed in Table 2.1, [5]. The table also contains types of acoustic emission sources.

Materials
Metals
Ceramics
Polymers
Composites (including those with metal, ceramic and polymer matrices and a wide variety of reinforcement materials)
Wood
Concrete
Rocks and geologic materials
Type of Sources
Microcrack
Macrocrack
Slip and dislocation movement
Fatigue
Corrosion
Delamination in layered media
Fault slip (Earthquakes)

Table 2.1 Materials show AE phenomena and types of sources triggering the emissions

2.2.1 Advantages of AE technique:

All methods of SHM have their own merits, in this section, some advantages of the acoustic emission method have been discussed.

- Susceptible to crack growth, which enables damage detection at initial stages.
- Possible to sense damage in complex geometries if sensors are located at suitable locations. To locate the emission source, the onset time of elastic waves at sensors can be used.
- A real-time SHM is possible, which allows the recording of the signals as soon as crack occurs, and uninterrupted data can be acquired for characterizing the source.
- The method can practically be applied to inspect engineering plants and other structures without stopping their functionality, e.g., an inspection of the pipeline can be completed without discontinuing the transportation of gas and liquid which rise operational costs.
- No outer force is necessary to excite the mechanical waves in the specimen.

2. 3 AE data analysis approaches

AE data can be analysed using two approaches which identified as: traditionally used **parameter-based** approach and another method **waveform-based** which is quite new and has encouraging outcome for data analysis.

2.3.1 Parameter based analysis

In this approach, the extent of damage can be assessed using signal parameters. Figure 2.2 represent typically used AE signal parameters. Some of the important time domain properties for the characterisation of structural damage are explained briefly.

Figure 2.2 Characteristic properties of time domain AE signals used for data analysis [10]

Threshold: Setting this parameter is crucial, otherwise signals with low amplitude can easily be lost if the threshold value is set too high and vice versa. Once the received signal reached at a set threshold value the recording of data is triggered by the data acquisition system.

Hit: It occurs when a signal surpasses the threshold and allows the data acquisition system to acquire raw data relating to the occurrence of AE.

Amplitude: Associated with the magnitude of the elastic wave; it is an important parameter used for data analysis [7]. Amplitude is presented in volts or in decibel scale where $1 \mu\text{V}$ at the sensor is defined as 0 dB.

$$dB = 20 \log \left(\frac{V_{max}}{1\mu V} \right) - (\text{Preamplifier gain in dB})$$

Equation 2.1

Rise time: A duration when a signal is triggered and reaches the maximum amplitude.

2.3.2 Waveform dependent AE data analysis

When using the parameter-dependent approach, recording the real signal is not trivial because only limited parameters of the signal are acquired. Fast data recording and a minimum amount of stored data are the main benefits for the parametric analysis of the AE signals. Now with the advancement in computing systems and availability of better sensors, we can perform quick and complete data acquisition [8].

Properties related to propagating medium change the waveform shape, but the characteristic properties of the source have not been lost, and waveform analysis can be expected to extract

this information and help to differentiate the AE sources. For the post-processing of the recorded data, frequency domain analysis gives further details in comparison to the time domain analysis. For frequency domain analysis Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) tool has been used more frequently. The only disadvantage of FFT is that it gives the main frequency components present in the signal but not their time of occurrences. To overcome this issue Short-Fast Fourier Transform (SFFT) tool is used mostly but it has a frequency resolution limitation, therefore another time-frequency analysis method is used called Wavelet Transform (WT).

AE signals are categorised in two basic types: continuous and burst signals, illustrated in Figure 2.3. Signals occurred for short periods are transient or bursts in nature while continuous signals occurred for an extended time duration. Fractures and cracks in a material usually cause transient signals and continuous signals are mainly noise signals [9].

Figure 2.3 Transient (left) and continuous (right) AE signal [9]

Plate geometry is often used in several engineering equipment. The fatigue crack is one of the main reasons to cause damage to them, initiating stress concentrations in the structure. If in time measures are not taken, a crack could accelerate under load conditions and eventually lead to structural failure/deterioration . Therefore, (SHM) is vital for retaining the reliability and safety of a structure.

Lamb waves inherited the characteristics to cover extended distance with reduced energy attenuation, and regard as one of the possible SHM method [36]. The existing linear Lamb wave method uses variation in acoustic velocity, mode transformation, time of flight (TOF), and transmission and reflection coefficients to identify obvious fatigue cracks, macroscopic holes, and notches [36]. This research work mainly focused on the Lamb waves-based method to characterise the raw AE data for simulated AE source locations in plate structures.

If the AE generated signals are larger than the noise, a simple method of threshold crossing can be used for determining the AE events. In general, a threshold voltage is set above the background noise signals, and when the rectified signal crosses the set threshold it is considered as an AE event and the time of occurrence of the event can be recorded. This method has an inherent error to estimate the arrival time because the amplitude of the AE event takes some time to increase to the set threshold and this introduced error in source location estimation.

The error in arrival time rises as the SNR reduces. To minimise this error different arrival time estimation methods have been explored mainly focused on statistical approaches which help to define a more accurate arrival time. These techniques include cross-correlation with an approximated AE source [11,12] and the Akaike information criterion [13-15] to find the distinction between background noise and actual AE event signal. All these methods improve the accuracy of the arrival time estimation. The implementation of these methods is not trivial and demand complex processing in comparison to the threshold crossing method. The statistical approaches required whole signal acquired from the structure to be processed and this involves much more complex hardware and more computational power. This is a disadvantage when only one data processing unit may require to cope with the signals obtained from several sensing devices.

2.4 Acoustic Emission Sensors

The acoustic emission sensors are used as sender or receiver of AE signals for material testing. They are designed as per application with a wide range of different active elements, elements diameters, main frequencies, bandwidths, and coupling methods [16,17].

For AE testing an effective coupling is required between the sensors and the test specimen. An efficient transfer of energy between sensors and test objects can be achieved using a variety of couplant like vacuum grease, liquid gel, gel pads and oil. A selection of sensors can be made as per application, for AE testing most of the signals occurred between the frequency range of 0.1-1 MHz [18].

For detecting flaws and damage in the test sample, the placement and selection of AE sensors must be optimised. The acoustic waves are more susceptible to attenuation when propagated in the transmission medium depending on the characteristics of the medium. This energy loss of the acoustic waves limits the separation distance between the sensors. Therefore, it is

necessary to identify the main areas of structures where the damage is most likely occurred and place the sensors efficiently.

AE sensors have either narrowband or broadband frequency responses. The use of both types of sensors is completely application oriented. Narrowband sensors have a better signal to noise ratio and are preferably used in practical applications and particular attention is required to select a suitable frequency range for narrowband sensors [20]. Broadband sensors cover a wide frequency spectrum with a low signal to noise ratio [19].

2.4.1 Contemporary Piezoelectric Sensors

AE sensors are made using a single, bulk piezo-electric element. Electrodes are sputtered at the top and bottom of the active material which is required to apply and sense electrical signals. One of the electrodes is connected to the external case of the sensor for electrical isolation. The active element is protected from any damage using a wear plate. The backing layer is used to minimise the reflection from the interference of the active element and the casing [21]. Figure 2.4 shows schematic of AE sensor.

Figure 2.4 Schematic of AE Sensor [10]

PZTs with a thickness greater than $100\mu\text{m}$ in thickness are used as active elements and considered as bulk PZT, they are of low cost in comparison to single crystal elements. Other advantages of using bulk PZT as AE sensors are listed here.

- For bulk PZT a thickness greater than $100\mu\text{m}$ allows greater grain size which improves material properties due to the higher ratio of piezoelectric material to grain boundary in the material [10,22].
- The loss of lead during high temperature processes can be reduced due to the greater volume to surface area ratio [10,23].

- Bulk PZT materials do not require any supportive structure or substrate to provide mechanical strength, therefore when stress is applied to the bulk material the properties are not degraded due to a different thermal expansion rate.

2.4.2 Development of new sensors

An increased application of structural health monitoring in different industries required the continuous development of new sensing technology. It is always paramount to design and develop cost-effective and miniaturised sensors because among other issues commercial sensors are found quite expensive and occasionally not fit for purpose due to their size and design [24,25]. Therefore, it is essential to find new ways of sensor designing and bring down the cost effectively and enable continuous monitoring using sensor arrays.

For this research work, the focus is given to thin film sensors, next in this section further discussion has been made on thin film sensors for the AE technique.

2.4.2.1 Thin Film Sensors

AE sensors made of the thin film of active material were used for examining aircraft structural components in the early 90's. The work as mentioned in [10,26] was carried out where integrated thin film devices were used to give alerts against component failure. Thin film of active material (PZT) was prepared at low temperature and found capable for MEMS AE applications; the work was carried out in 1999. The findings of these works suggested a promising future of thin film-based AE sensors, the possible disadvantage of thin film devices is their low sensitivity in comparison to the bulk piezoelectric sensors. The low sensitivity of thin film materials is due to lower magnitude than those of bulk material.

The use of piezoelectric thin film materials, like zinc oxide (ZnO) and aluminium nitride (AlN) for designing sensing devices gain more attention recently [27,28]. A variety of substrates, like metal, ceramics, silicon, or glass are used for the deposition of thin films and miniaturised sensing devices are made for non-destructive testing. The thin films of metal oxides can also be deposited on a flexible substrate such as metal foils and aid to make physically flexible thin film sensors. This could solve conventional problems associated with commercial AE sensors including their size and shape, coupling to complex test geometries and operating temperature limitations. However, the deposition of metal oxide on thin flexible substrates and acoustic performance of the flexible AE devices needs to be investigated widely.

To operate effectively as an AE sensor, the thin film PZT should be deposited of high quality. By using different deposition techniques, we can obtain practically all the properties of the thin film and modify them. Depending on the area of application the deposition techniques are varied because they do not result in identical properties such as microstructure, surface morphology, optical, corrosion and hardness [29,30].

In the area of thin film, different types of deposition techniques are in use and with each technique, the appropriate consideration needs to be given for the good quality of the thin film. In this research work, the focal point is on the deposition of thin film on a micron scale, the two frequently used deposition methods are prioritised and discussed in brief. The two main subsets of deposition techniques are physical vapour deposition (PVD) and chemical vapour deposition (CVD). In PVD, atoms and molecules play their role to make vapour that deposit on the substrate, and for CVD, the thin film on the substrate is the result of the vapour undergoing a chemical reaction [31-35]. Figure 2.5 shows the type of thin film deposition which are in the gaseous state, solution state, and molten or semi-molten state.

Figure 2.5 Variations of thin film deposition technique

2.5 Conclusions

AE has the potential to be used as a structural health monitoring tool. However, effective analysis of a large volume of data generated during testing remains a challenging issue. It is found that most of the existing AE monitoring technology depend on bulk piezoelectric elements and is sometimes not suitable for the examining of complex geometries and test specimens in harsh environments.

The review of related literature conducted in this chapter reveals that the work has been conducted on the miniaturisation of AE devices through thin film technology, but still, there is a need of expertise and knowledge regarding the use of thin film sensing devices for AE measurements.

Thin film technology does have the capability to minimise the problems related to commercially available AE sensors, the main drawback of thin film devices is the use of a smaller amount of piezoelectric material which led to the devices produced low piezoelectric properties and make the devices less sensitive to detect AE events in various applications.

To compete commercially with other existing devices, thin film sensing technology needs to exhibit reasonable sensitivity and offer other advantages over commercial solutions. A good understanding of the positives and negatives of different sensor types help to make sure the correct answer for AE detection deployment.

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CHAPTER 3

Instrumentation for acoustic emission system

3.1 Introduction

Detection, amplification, filtering and analysing of signals are some of the important issues in AE technology [1]. As mentioned earlier, the primary blocks for AE testing are comprised of sensing devices, signal conditioning and data acquisition. Sensors are coupled to the test specimen using appropriate couplant for efficient detection of acoustic waves. Because these waves attenuate quickly and have a small amplitude, signal conditioning can be carried out before feeding the signals into the acquisition system [2].

This research is focused on the detection and localization of simulated AE sources in the metal plate using in-house developed thin film AE sensors. The output of each sensor would link to a pre-amplifier circuit block where the signal was filtered and amplified. The proposed pre-amplifier design helps to amplify the signal up to 55 dB. The selection of components for circuit development was made to minimize the overall propagation delay of the AE prototype system. The software based logical trigger approach was also introduced which aids to minimize the loss of meaning full data which is often lost due to AE wave's attenuation.

3.2 Pre-amplifiers circuits design

The signal conditioning circuits were designed and built for the AE prototype system with a high gain value of approximately 55 dB, the high gain value for the pre-amplifier was primarily selected due to the off-resonance operation for the thin film sensors at a lower frequency range. To analyse the recorded AE data from the broadband thin film sensors, the bandpass filters were designed with high pass and low pass frequencies of 0.02 and 1 MHz respectively.

The designing of both electronic circuits (pre-amp & band-pass filter) was included theoretical aspects, electronic components selection, designing of schematic diagrams, designing of the circuit using a breadboard, testing of the circuits, components soldering on Eurocard, and last cabling and housing of the circuits.

Initially, the theoretical aspects were covered. This stage included a mathematical calculation for circuit designing. For example, the circuit gain was calculated using equation 3.1 [3], for the desired gain value of 55 dB the values of the resistors were selected.

$$A = 1 + \frac{R_f}{R_1}$$

Equation 3.1

Where R_f , R_1 simply made a potential divider network across the non-inverting amplifier.

Similarly, calculations were carried out for designing the band pass filter circuits. Firstly, the passive components values were calculated for lower cut-off and upper cut-off frequencies using equation 3.2 [2].

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi RC}$$

Equation 3.2

For the pre-amplifier circuit, it was crucial to select an op-amp with a high gain bandwidth product (GBWP). The gain-bandwidth product for an amplifier is the product of the amplifier's bandwidth and the gain at which the bandwidth is measured [3]. The selected Op-amp has a wide bandwidth and maximum gain-bandwidth product of 300MHz (datasheet included in Appendix C).

After selecting the required electronic components, ADIsimPE 8.2 (SIMETRIX simulation) from Analog Devices was used to design the schematic diagram for pre-amplifier with integrated bandpass filter and then circuit simulation was conducted. This software can be used for SPICE and mix mode simulation [4]. The designed circuit diagram using SIMetrix is shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Circuit diagram for Pre-amplifier with integrated band pass filter, the design was made using SIMetrix design tool

For over three decades integrated circuit design engineers have been using analogue simulation software SPICE. In a fast-engineering production environment, it is essential to use simulation software to save both time and costs [4]. To make this research study more cost-effective and time-efficient the SIMetrix simulation was used to examine the performance of an in-house designed pre-amplifier circuit before building the real circuit.

When using the SIMetrix simulation tool, a choice of analysis modes was available. For the above-designed circuit, *transient analysis* was used because it is closely related to the bench testing of the circuit. To study the behaviour of the designed circuit, the input signal consists of a sine wave of 4mV peak to peak amplitude with varying frequency from 0.002 to 1 MHz range with a step of 0.05 MHz was defined in the analysis edit window. After completing the simulation run, the output voltage of the circuit was investigated over the defined analysis time. Figure 3.2 shows the circuit simulation setup with input waveform editing window and analysis selection window. The output voltage of the circuit was recorded, the gain of the circuit was calculated, and the response of the circuit was plotted for the frequency. Figure 3.3 shows the simulation results as gain vs frequency plot for the in-house designed pre-amplifier circuit with integrated bandpass filter.

Figure 3.2 Circuit simulation setup with the windows for the selections of analysis type (transient analysis) and input editing window (sine wave)

Figure 3.3 Simulated gain vs frequency response for in-house designed pre-amplifier circuit; output voltage value was recorded with the 0.05 MHz frequency steps while the input voltage 4 mV was kept constant, -3dB bandwidth was ~ 0.7 MHz

Figure 3.3 reveals that at 0.001 MHz the circuit gain was around 20 dB which increased gradually to 52 dB as the frequency reached 0.05 MHz, increment of 32 dB in the gain indicating the high pass filter characteristics. From 0.1 to 0.5 MHz the gain value found a maximum ~ 55 dB which indicated the bandpass filter behaviour of the circuit. From 0.5 to 1.0 MHz the simulated circuit gain was reduced steadily from 55 to 40 dB respectively. This decrement of gain with increment in frequency indicated the low pass filter response. The large frequency bandwidth of the filter (B.W._{-3 dB} ~ 0.7 MHz) was selected due to the broadband nature of the thin film transducers used in this study. The circuit simulation was not conducted beyond 1 MHz because it was designed to aid AE testing within the spectrum of 0.02-1 MHz.

As per the schematic, the circuits were designed on breadboard. The amplifier circuit was designed and tested. Function generator, oscilloscope and dual 5V DC power supply was used to study the circuit response. Similarly, a filter circuit was designed and checked. Finally, both circuits were integrated on breadboard and the combined response of both circuits was studied.

Afterwards, the components for both circuits were soldered on strips board and tested again, and then necessary cabling and housing for the circuit was performed. The complete circuit with housing is shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4 Pre-amplifier circuit, (a) components on strips board, (b) with cabling and housing

The performance of the designed circuit was characterized in the lab; the frequency generator was used to generate the input signal for frequencies from 0.001 to 1.0 MHz. A sine wave with constant peak to peak amplitude of 4mV was used as an input signal to the amplifier, and then the output of the circuit was recorded at every 0.05 MHz step using a PicoScope-3000 series USB oscilloscope (Pico Technology Ltd). The spreadsheet was used to plot the calculated voltage gain versus frequency. Figure 3.5 shows the gain vs frequency response of the amplifier circuit, at 0.001 MHz the gain was observed 15 dB, and then at 0.05 MHz the amplification was observed around 50 dB. The circuit gain response was observed maximum of around 55 dB (± 1 dB) between 0.1-0.5 MHz. Afterwards, the gain was gradually decreased from 53 to 40 dB for the frequency ranges between 0.5 to 1 MHz respectively. The signals outside of 0.02 and 1 MHz frequencies have been discriminated by this circuit.

Figure 3.5 Gain vs Frequency response of the in-house developed pre-amplifier; output voltage value was recorded with the 0.05 MHz frequency steps while the input voltage was kept constant to 4 mV, -3dB bandwidth was ~ 0.6 MHz

3.3 Programmable triggering approach for AE data acquisition

Advancement in technology flourishes the growth of embedded systems by introducing different hardware and software components in them. Usually, specific tasks are associated with the embedded system, and are built of inputs, control processing units and outputs. Examples like the mobile industry, aerospace industry and automobiles are all embedded systems based.

For the application phase of the embedded systems, it is necessary to have an accurate design of architecture and system model. Different approaches are available which can help to quickly design and implement the process of embedded systems, for example, Computer-Aided Design, used for engineering structures analysis and P-Spice, used for different circuits simulation. Also, the number of embedded devices that can be interacted with the physical world to control the range of the functions have achieved staggering growth with the development of microcontroller-based easy-to-use designed systems which are the inexpensive and less complex alternative for the old designed systems with complicated electronic circuits. One of the most used embedded devices is Arduino.

In this research work, an Arduino UNO (datasheet included in Appendix C) open-source tool was used to sense and control the triggering mechanism for recording the AE events. The open-source hardware has shown an ability to meet the need for accurate and real-time AE data recording from an array of thin film sensors.

The functionality of the approach is illustrated in Figure 3.6. The output of each sensor was linked to a pre-amplifier circuit block where the signal was filtered and amplified by approximately a gain of 55 dB. Sequentially, each output of the conditioning circuit would compare to set reference voltage. OR digital logic would apply to the compared results, the logic could become high if one or more signals from sensing nodes cross the set reference voltage and trigger the acquisition system to acquire data from all three sensors and stored it. This approach allows flexibility for the users to set reference voltages as per observed noise levels from the surrounding.

Figure 3.6 Illustration for the proposed trigger mechanism using Arduino UNO

3.3.1 Arduino

Arduino is a very useful tool for embedded system growth and can be implemented to perform different tasks, for example, monitoring environmental parameters: humidity and temperature, greenhouse monitoring, robots and so on. Unlike other programmable circuit boards, the Arduino does not require separate programmer, simply USB cable is used to load the codes onto the board. The subsequent paragraphs highlight the main components on the Arduino UNO board used in this project.

The Arduino boards have diverse pins architecture, each of which has unique name and can be used for variety of operations. GND (Pin3), ground pin which can be used to make ground connection with the external circuits. 5V (Pin4) and 3V (Pin5), both pins are used to supply the power to run the Arduino as per system requirements. Pins A0-A5, these are analogue pins and read analogue data from different analogue sensors, like in this project from thin film transducers. Digital (Pin 0-13), these pins can be used for both digital input and output.

The Arduino is a microcontroller-based board. This AVR microcontroller chip is known as ATmega328PU (datasheet included in Appendix C). The microcontroller-based architecture of Arduino makes it easy to use and popular for different kind of embedded system projects.

3.3.2 Arduino internal development environment (IDE)

To draft various types of programming codes and load them into the Arduino microcontroller, the IDE is a programming environment that allows users to do so [7] and utilized the Processing programming language. IDE provides functionality to interpret the programme coding to the assembler language and upload the program to the Arduino microcontroller. Built-in function for code correction checks the written programme for any error [6]. After the programme has been tested it is ready to upload to the Arduino using the USB cable that varies in different models [7].

Arduino software (IDE) is used to write the programs called sketches [6]. In the text editor, these sketches are written and saved. The main features of the editor are cutting/pasting and searching/replacing text. While saving and exporting the sketches the message area gives feedbacks and displays errors. The available toolbar uses to open, create, save, and upload sketches and open the serial monitor.

In any sketch of Arduino **setup ()** and **loop ()** are two main functions. Initially, the **setup ()** function is used to set up opening settings and runs only a single time when switch-on the device. Once the **setup ()** run, the **loop ()** function is ready to run, it contains the main functionality of the logic written in sketch and run repeatedly until power off. IDE environment contained an extensive programme code database, also the number of open-source libraries are offered from the Arduino community [5,6].

3.3.3 Software approach for logical trigger using IDE

The software approach defines roles to administrate trigger mechanism to read analogue data from AE sensors. In this section the software approach is illustrated with the help of flow chart.

Figure 3.7 Flow chart illustrated software approach for logical triggering of data acquisition

As mentioned earlier, this logical triggering approach was used to robust the AE system. Available commercial AE systems often use one of the in-service AE transducers as a triggering transducer. The drawback of using one of the in-service transducers as a trigger is quite clear. For example, in the evaluation of large structural health monitoring if any AE event happened which is quite far from triggering transducer in that case there is ample chance that this event data may be lost because AE waves attenuate quickly as they travel and if they don't reach to the triggering transducer the data acquisition system will not record the event. Also, this approach helps to manage memory space for the recorded AE data, usually, the AE events contain a large amount of data which take up large memory space, especially in the case of continuous monitoring. This approach helps to overcome these problems and allow real-time AE events monitoring. Programme coding written using IDE is included in Appendix A.

3.4 Conclusions

Because of the complexity of the structure and random occurrence of emission sources, it might be possible that some AE events can easily be missed. Therefore, it is vital to couple the sensors test specimen at the locations which are more susceptible to damage and flaws. Due to the dispersive nature, the acoustic waves attenuated quickly and merged into the noise floor quickly. Therefore, the traditional acquisition system is not enough to gather all meaning full information to detect and locate AE events with a minimum percentage of error.

Considering the basic instrumentation of the acoustic emission system with advancements, for this research work the AE prototype system was developed in-house. The bespoke prototype would be proficient to detect and locate AE sources using an array of the bespoke AE thin film sensors and commercial AE sensors with the gain setting of up to 55 dB and bandpass filter response with -3 dB bandwidth of 0.6 MHz. An Arduino based embedded device was built to trigger the data acquisition system for recording the AE propagating signals with minimum attenuation.

3.5 References

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CHAPTER 4

Broadband thin films AE sensors for acoustic emission based structural health monitoring

4.1 Introduction

Piezoelectric transducers have been used for many years for condition monitoring by recording acoustic emissions from damaged parts. Probes used for these examinations are usually bulky devices which, in some cases, are incapable to fit into awkward locations or survive in the environment where the part is operating.

In this work, passive devices have been investigated which are fabricated from piezoelectric thin films deposited directly onto the aluminium foil substrate. Zinc oxide (ZnO) thin films were used, deposited by RF magnetron sputtering under vacuum [6]. By this technique, a polycrystalline film a few microns thick is formed and, unlike usual piezoceramic materials, does not require poling. The thin-film sensing devices do not operate in a $\lambda/2$ thickness resonant mode like conventional piezoelectric transducers. Instead, they operate far below their resonant frequency in a regime where the input signal, plus electrical and mechanical effects, controls the electro-acoustic characteristics of the device [6].

The first part of this chapter covers the deposition and characterisation of ZnO thin film elements on the substrate of different thicknesses. After this, the chapter focuses on the fabrication of stand-alone sensing devices. To demonstrate the potential of produced sensing devices they were used for AE source detection and location and benchmarked with commercially available AE sensors UT-1000 (Physical Acoustic Ltd), datasheet included in Appendix C. All the experiments were performed in the lab environment and closely mimic to the real-life scenarios.

4.2 Design and development of the metal oxide thin film sensors

4.2.1 Zinc Oxide

It is a semiconducting material with a wide direct bandgap of $\sim 3.3\text{-}3.4$ eV [1,2] and a non-centrosymmetric hexagonal wurtzite crystal structure Figure 4.1 [1]. Materials are counted to have wide band gaps if their bandgap energy is considerably greater than that of the common semiconductors like silicon 1.1 eV and gallium arsenide 1.4 eV [3]. Wider bandgap materials like zinc oxide, silicon carbide, gallium nitride, and diamond are more efficient in high power and high temperature applications [4]. It is a widely used material in various applications such as gas sensors, UV resistive coatings, piezoelectric devices, varistors, surface acoustic wave (SAW) devices and transparent conductive oxide electrodes [1].

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Ellmer, Klaus, Andreas Klien and Bernd Rech. 'ZnO and Its Applications'. Transparent Conductive Zinc Oxide. Springer, 2008. 1-33.

Figure 4.1 Hexagonal wurtzite crystal structure which gives ZnO its unique piezoelectric properties [1]

ZnO is getting reputation and replacing piezoelectric materials such as indium tin oxide (ITO) is gradually expensive. ZnO can be deposited in various ways like chemical vapour deposition and physical vapour deposition. Another attraction of ZnO is that it is biocompatible and lead free, not like other conventional piezoelectric materials PZT and barium titanate (BaTiO₃).

4.2.2 Zinc oxide thin films deposition

Deposition can be achieved using various methods, such as physical vapour deposition, chemical vapour deposition, pulsed laser, and electrochemical [9]. Once deposited, this piezoelectric material is polycrystalline, and the crystals normally form a columnar structure and must be likewise allocated, and c-axis oriented to act as piezoelectric material.

Thin films were sputtered using a plasma-assisted DC sputtering system which is a physical vapour deposition method (PVD). The machine used for this purpose is known as Nordiko 3750 as shown in Figure 4.2 . It features a rotating six-sided substrate holding drum on the turntable in the chamber with variable rotating speeds (1-10) as shown in Figure 4.3, the sputtering system support two magnetron targets of size 100 x 300 mm².

Figure 4.2 Nordiko 3750, DC sputtering system

Figure 4.3 (a) Rotating six-sided substrate holding drum on turntable in the chamber (b) Variable rotating speed control knob with on and off switching mechanism for turntable

DC sputtering is a method of physical vapour deposition, starts from a momentum transfer of fast-moving ions striking with a cathode or target material. Basically, the high-speed ions struck the surface of the target and trigger the expulsion of the topmost atoms of the target [7]. DC sputtering starts with the start of a glow expansion or plasma because of a large DC bias between a cathode and an anode under a vacuum, Figure 4.4 [8]. In this case, a pure zinc target is the cathode of the system, and the chamber of the vacuum system is the anode. Once a vacuum has been achieved, the desired ratio of high purity Ar and O₂ gas is injected into the chamber. This allows the target to oxidize into ZnO and as the argon and oxygen ions collide with the target, they will sputter a ZnO thin film onto the substrate's surface.

Figure 4. 4 Deposition phenomena for the ZnO thin film using physical vapor deposition (PVD), or sputtering[8].

Extensive research work has been done at TFSI in the University of the West of Scotland which demonstrated the capability of sputtered ZnO film sensors for various NDT applications. [9-16]. In this research work sputtering parameters were optimised as a continuation of our research group work targeted to develop good quality ZnO thin film for durable NDT application. To achieve those parameters small test runs were carried out and Table 4.1 indicates the parameters used in this research work.

Plasma Power (kW)	Reactive gases	Ar/O ₂ ratio (Standard Cubic Centimetre per Minute)	Distance between Zn targets and foil substrate (cm)	Substrate pre-heating	No. of Zn targets	Deposition rate (nm/H)	Turntable speed
0.4	Ar & O ₂	7.5/13	10	No	2	400	4

Table 4.1 Selection of parameters for sputtering ZnO thin films using NORDIKO -3750 DC sputtering system

During the sputtering process, the substrate holder was rotated and encouraged the uniform deposition of thin films. The masking technique was used for sputtering the thin films and provided sufficient surface area of the substrate which was used as a ground electrode.

The aluminium plate with the dimensions like the substrate holder of NORDIKO 3750 (152 x 101.6) mm² was used as a mask and holes were drilled in a matrix of 6 rows and 4 columns. These holes were 10 mm apart from each other horizontally and vertically. The foil substrate was sandwiched between the masking plate and substrate holder of NORDIKO. The masking allowed sputtering of ZnO in a circular shape with a diameter of 8 mm. The film was sputtered evenly to the substrate through the drilled holes, because of the rotating substrate holding drum on the turntable in the chamber.

4.2.3 Zinc oxide thin films characterisation

The deposited thin films were characterised for piezoelectric application. The structural properties of the films were characterised to analyse the size of the crystals, the thickness of the films, and the physical structure.

With cross-sectional scanning electron microscope (SEM) imaging and profilometer scans, the thickness of the film would find as shown in Figure 4.5 (a). The magnified image taken from scanning electron microscope (SEM) Hitachi S4100, the system has a magnification of 40,000 times, a resolution of 1.5mm and acceleration voltage for primary electrons of up to 30kV. The Al foil remained wrinkle free after the deposition, suggesting low internal stress. Foil ductility and flexibility was virtually unaffected. The film has formed a dense polycrystalline columnar microstructure, with the growth direction aligned normal to the substrate surface (c-axis orientation) which is crucial for the films to act as a piezoelectric material, as discussed in the literature [17].

X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a material characterization technique that is used to determine the crystalline quality, chemical composition, and atomic structure of a solid material. The analysis was carried out using a Siemens D5000 with CuK α radiation (40kV, 30mA). The diffraction angle was set between 20 & 60 degrees with 1 scan (count) per second at 0.2° increments. Figure 4.5(b) shows the XRD spectrum with two indicating peaks, the first intense and narrow diffraction peak occurred at 2θ approximately 34.4° which indicates single crystalline behaviour of the ZnO film. The second peak occurred at 2θ approximately 45° related to Al foil substrate. These peaks measurements and the values of 2θ were found in good commitment with the results reported in works of literatures [16-20].

Figure 4.5 (a) SEM image, cross-section of columnar structure of approximately 6 μm thickness film on 50 μm thick Al foil (b) XRD pattern of the as-deposited ZnO thin film deposited when using Ar/O₂ ratio (7.5:13 sccm) (c) shows the XRD pattern when using Ar/O₂ ratio (7:3 sccm)

4.2.4 Effect of substrate thickness on the performance of the thin films AE sensors

In this section the impact of different substrate thicknesses on the performance of the thin films AE sensors was investigated. As an example, the sputtered ZnO thin films on 75 μm thick flexible Al foil substrate is shown in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6 Sputtered ZnO thin film approximately 6 μm thin on Al foil substrate of thickness 75 μm . The mask technique was allowed deposition of thin films with 8mm diameter after every 20 mm gap, the masking was used to utilise maximum surface area of the metal foil for electrical ground

For the top electrode, a thin layer of chromium/gold was sputtered onto the top of ZnO thin films using the K575 Turbo Sputter Coater system (Emitech Ltd. Ashford, Kent, UK). The main parts of the sputtering system are shown in Figure 4.7. The sputtering requires the collision of thermally charged electrons with static gas ions which then accelerate towards the gold & chromium target. A high voltage is used across the low-pressure gas to create plasma which releases gold atoms so that they can be deposited onto the sample [21]. The inert gas used in the procedure is Argon. The thickness of the electrode is controlled by the length of time the sample is left under the plasma. The sample was left under the plasma for 2½ minutes, and the electrode layer coating achieved approximately 400 nm thick.

Figure 4.7 K575X Turbo Sputter Coater System

Figure 4.8 (a) Zoomed view indicates top electrode onto the disc-like ZnO thin film element, (b) illustration of thin films device with top and bottom electrodes

Figure 4.8(a) shows a zoomed view of the disk-like thin film element with a sputtered top electrode of 400 nm thick. An illustration of the complete thin film device with a top and bottom electrode is shown in Figure 4.8(b). This pattern of the electrodes encourages the generation of longitudinal waves travelling through the entire thickness of the device. The electrodes designed for the thin film devices were made to encourage the propagation of longitudinal waves through the whole thickness of the sensing device.

Next, by using E5061B Network Analyser from KEYSIGHT Ltd. as shown in Figure 4.9, the reflection coefficient (S_{11}) measurements were carried out. The S_{11} represents signal loss when travelling through the test device and it is measured in decibels (dB).

S_{11} parameter for flexible thin film devices was measured using a specially designed test fixture as shown in Figure 4.10, it can be connected directly to the network analyser using a BNC male probe and required no extra cables. The metal plate of the fixture provides mechanical support to the flexible foil substrate and electrical ground connectivity once it meets the bottom face of the metal foil. The other metal pin attached to the top electrode excited the ZnO piezoelectric thin film electrically in thickness mode.

Figure 4.9 E5061B Network Analyser from KEYSIGHT Ltd

Figure 4.10 Specially designed test fixture for measuring S_{11} parameter, the flexible thin film device sandwiched between the metal plate and pin, where metal plate used to make electrical ground and metal pin connected to top electrode to excite the thin film electrically

S_{11} spectra simulation for the thin film's devices was carried out using the One-Dimensional Model (ODM) as well. In the software, the solution of the 1-D wave equation is based on frequency domain matrix formulation. This modelling approach (ODM, the University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, UK) predict the electrical and acoustic characteristics of multilayer sensing device structures by allowing the combination of active and passive layers [22,23].

Three thin film sensing devices with 50,75 & 100 μm thick Al foil substrate have been simulated and results were compared to the experimental S_{11} measurements. The material properties used for the simulation is mentioned in Table 4.2.

Parameters	Piezoelectric material (ZnO thin film)	Substrate (Al foil)
Density, ρ (kgm^{-3})	5680	2700
Thickness mode velocity, V_L (ms^{-1})	6026	6300
Elastic stiffness, C_{33} (10^{11}Nm^{-2})	2.11	0.46
Thickness (μm)	approximately 6	50,75,100
Attenuation, A (dB/cm)	1	0.8
Acoustic impedance, Z (Mrayl)	36.44	17.06

Table 4.2 Material properties of the ZnO thin films devices used in simulation [24,25]

The experimental and simulated S_{11} spectra for the thin film devices of different substrate thicknesses are shown in Figure 4.11. The graphs indicated multiple reverberations associated with the thickness mode resonances of the thin film devices. The occurrence of resonance frequency peaks found approximately the same for simulated and measured S_{11} spectra as shown in the inset in each graph, the small discrepancy between simulated and measured frequency peaks might be seen because no electrodes were added in ODM modelling.

The reverberation phenomenon occurred due to the bouncing of longitudinal waves inside the substrate. From the graphs in Figure 4.11, it was observed that with the increased substrate thickness the reverberations occurred more quickly due to increased wavelength; the resonance frequency decreased gradually as the substrate thickness increased from 50 to 75 & 100 μm . It was observed that with increased substrate thickness the reflection loss values were increased because most of the transmitted signal bounced inside the thick substrate and less energy transmitted to the active element.

Figure 4.11 Measured (in blue colour) and simulated (in orange colour) S_{11} spectra shown multiple thickness mode reverberations in the Al foil substrate, (a) for the thin film device with substrate thickness of 50 μm , the inset shows single resonance peak for simulated and measured spectrum, (b) for the thin film device with substrate thickness of 75 μm , the inset shows occurrence of two resonance peaks for simulated and measured spectrum and (c) for the thin film device with substrate thickness of 100 μm , the inset shows occurrence of three resonance peaks for simulated and measured spectrum

4.3 ZnO thin films AE sensors design and fabrication steps

Disk-like thin films elements were cut out from the ZnO/Al elements. To provide mechanical support and avoid uneven foil substrate the thin film elements were glued on the glass slides using wax. A metal ring with an internal diameter of 10 mm was bonded to each ZnO/Al foil element. The metal ring was placed on top of the sputtered film area and the base of the metal ring was attached to the Al foil substrate using silver loaded epoxy (RS Pro Silver 10 g Vial Epoxy Conductive Adhesive), as shown in Figure 4.12(a). Once the epoxy was cured the structure became mechanically strong and the metal ring attached with the substrate would be used as the ground connection for the rest of the sensor assembly. Inside the metal ring, an 8 mm diameter area of the sputtered thin film was served as piezoelectric material. A small blob of silver paint approximately 4mm in diameter was applied at the top surface of the thin film with the help of a cocktail stick, the applied silver paint was acted as a back electrode. The one end of thin copper wire was attached to the back electrode and the second end was left free for later fabrication steps. At the front face of the sensor, the metal foil was not bonded to any traditional wear plate to maximise the acoustic impedance matching, especially when examining the metal test specimen.

To provide mechanical support to the thin copper wire and avoid punctures in the foil substrate, tungsten loaded epoxy was used as a backing layer this would also reduce the ringing effect inside the substrate. As tungsten is a conductive material, therefore it was first tested by mixing

the fine tungsten powder having particle size 6 μm with Araldite epoxy for non-conductivity. The acoustic impedance of the composite could be altered by changing the percentage content of tungsten in the mix, i.e., higher tungsten content means higher density and therefore higher impedance. To match the impedance of the tungsten/epoxy to that of the ZnO the percentage tungsten in this project was used around 5% of the total volume. The passive material was filled inside the metal ring and left overnight for curing, as shown in Figure 4.12(b).

The metal housing made of copper was used to cover the internal assembly of the sensor, the housing was made push fit to the internal metal ring for proper attachment between internal and outer assemblies. Similarly, a copper metal lid assembled with an SMA connector was made to push-fit with metal housing. The second end of the thin copper wire is now soldered with the SMA connector to receive the AE signals from the active material. The whole assembly was taken off from the glass slide once the thin film sensor was ready, as shown in Figure 4.12(c).

Figure 4.12 (a) Internal components of the thin film transducer (b) Added tungsten epoxy to provide mechanical support to the sensor structure and minimize reverberations inside the substrate (c) Complete assembly of the thin film sensor with push-fit outer case and SMA connector

4.3.1 Bespoke thin films AE sensors electrical properties characterization

Once the sensors were made ready, the electrical characterisation was performed using Agilent impedance analyser Model 4294A (Agilent Technologies, South Queensferry, UK). This model of impedance analyser has a maximum frequency range limit up to 110 MHz, even it does not work properly for the measurements above 100 MHz due to internal machine error. For accurate test measurements, the impedance analyser was calibrated before each use and impedance and phase data were acquired.

Once the calibration was completed impedance versus frequency sweep (0-1 MHz) was carried out on the thin films AE sensors and commercially available AE sensor UT-1000 AE sensor

(Physical Acoustic Ltd.). The absolute impedance magnitude trace and impedance phase trace were measured by selecting the $|Z|-\theta_z$ measurement parameter on the impedance analyser. After collecting the data from the impedance analyser, the graphs were plotted using an excel spreadsheet as shown in Figure 4.13.

The thin film AE sensor exhibited a capacitance response for the selected frequency range 20 Hz-1 MHz, as shown in Figure 4.13(a). The first longitudinal resonance frequency peak was expected at around 54 MHz, using the thickness of the ZnO/Al (approximately 56 μm) and the speed of sound in ZnO - 6026 ms^{-1} . It was observed that the resonance frequency of the thin film AE sensors occurred well above the frequency range used for AE testing (0.1-1) MHz [26]. The flat, capacitance type response of the thin film AE sensors within low frequency regime made them appropriate for the characterization of the acoustic emission signal properties for wide spectrum but the effectiveness of the sensor decreased when sensing the low energy acoustic waves due to the damping effect.

On the other hand, several peaks in the response of the UT-1000 AE sensor were observed between 100 kHz and 900 kHz, as shown in Figure 4.13(b). Initially in the graph small perturbation occurred which might be present due to the lateral mode but the largest perturbation in the impedance magnitude on y-axis suggested the thickness mode vibrations of the transducer. From the graph, it was found that the impedance magnitude curve shows thickness mode resonance frequency occurred around 0.3 MHz, the phase vs frequency plot indicates that the phase set above -90° as the sensing device achieved resonance. The parallel resonance frequency occurred around 0.33 MHz, the phase response was found around -40° and the sensor was behaving like an inductor. Ideally, the transducer behaves perfect capacitor if phase is set at -90° and becomes resistive if the phase is set at 0° , if the phase is set at $+90^\circ$ the sensor behaves as a perfect inductor.

The small perturbations were also observed at higher frequency > 0.35 MHz which is considered as a property for UT-1000 wideband AE sensor. Because the sensor response was not flat within the frequency range of interest it would show good sensing for low energy acoustic waves.

Figure 4.13 Frequency sweep vs impedance and phase for (a) the thin film AE sensor and (b) UT-1000 AE sensor

4.4 Thin film sensors repeatability tests

The performance of the bespoke thin film sensing device was analysed. A simple experiment was conducted where the sensing device was coupled to 3 mm thick mild steel plate using vacuum grease as a couplant. Artificial AE sources for the tests were generated using the ball drop method. A steel ball with a diameter of 3mm and weight 0.13 grams was used in the ball impact test to stimulate an impulse like force. The ball drop method was selected to generate high energy acoustic waves at low frequencies without compromising the sensing characteristics of the thin films AE sensors. For the repeatability of the simulated AE source, a plastic tube was used with a small hole of 10 mm diameter and a fixed height of 134 mm, the approach was used to improve the positioning repeatability and to prevent the ball from being lost on subsequent bounces. The raw AE data were acquired using an in-house developed AE system. Figure 4.14 indicates time domain waveforms for consecutive 10 simulated AE events overlaid on top of each other. The graph in Figure 4.15 represents the discrepancy in the peak amplitude of the acquired 10 shots. The data in Table 4.3 represents more confidence in the repeatability performance and suggested the two standard deviations approximately 10-times smaller than the mean peak amplitude value of 10-shots.

Figure 4.14 Consecutive 10 simulated AE events using ball drop method. The waveforms overlaid on top of each other to analyse the repeatability of the thin film sensing device

Figure 4.15 Variations in the peak amplitude for the consecutive 10-shots (ball drops)

No. of Shot	Peak Amp	Mean Peak Amp	STDEV (δ)	2δ
1	0.3079			
2	0.31974			
3	0.29604			
4	0.32763			
5	0.2842			
6	0.3079			
7	0.3			
8	0.280265			
9	0.288155			
10	0.331585	0.3	0.017	0.03

Table 4.3 Table represents peak amplitude for each ball drop event, also included the mean of the peak amplitudes and variation in the data

4.5 Proposed method of testing and data analysis

To prove the concept of AE testing, the in-house developed thin film AE sensors were utilised for detecting AE sources in the plate like structures and locating them by using Lamb wave-based analysis. The data analysis algorithm proposed in this study is summarised in Figure 4.16. For the acquired raw AE data, frequency domain analysis as a function of time was carried out, such as short time Fourier transform (STFT) and wavelet transform (WT).

Figure 4.16 Flow chart representing AE data analysis steps

4.6 Experiments for linear source location

In this study the lab experiments were performed to detect and locate linear AE sources in plate-like structure. The aluminium plate had dimensions of ($L=0.8$ m) by ($W=0.5$ m) and a thickness of ($H=3$ mm) was used as a test specimen. Both sensors were positioned away from the boundaries of the plate to minimize signal reflection and avoid signal complexity. For improved acoustic coupling between the sensors and test specimen, a vacuum grease was used as a couplant. The in-house developed AE prototype system was used for data acquisition. The PICOScope-3000 series from (PICO Technology Ltd.) was used for data acquisition with a sampling rate of 1 MHz for 2 ms which allows the acquisition of 2000 data points, and an in-house developed AE prototype system was used for data acquisition. Because the triggering block was programmable, the reference voltage as per measured noise level would be set by the user. In the lab environment, the set reference level was measured at 70mV and used as the set reference threshold voltage. Figure 4.17 illustrates the schematic for linear source location in the test specimen. The sensors and source locations with x and y coordinates are represented in Table 4.4.

Figure 4.17 Plate schematic with known source and thin film AE sensor locations, top view

Transducers & Sources	XY coordinates m (± 5 mm)
1 st Transducer (S_1)	(0.21,0.0)
2 nd Transducer 2 (S_2)	(0.730,0.0)
AE Source	(0.110,0.0)

Table 4.4 Thin film sensors and AE source locations, indicating X & Y coordinates

For AE source simulation, the pencil lead break (PLB) method was utilised, also known as the Hsu-Nielsen source. Breaking of lead give transient signals like the real AE source and can be adopted easily in the lab environment. AE signals were generated by breaking 0.7mm pencil leads at the selected location on the plate, the lead break tests were performed five times to check the repeatability. The pencil was kept using special fitting made of aluminium, also known as Nielsen Shoe, as shown in Figure 4.18, the shoe aids to break the lead at the same angle from the surface with similarly applied force.

Figure 4.18 Pencil with suitable fitting of shoe for pencil lead break tests

The arrival time difference between the sensors was calculated using the cross-correlation method, the algorithm was written in MATLAB (as shown in Appendix A). For frequency domain analysis wavelet transforms (WT) was carried out to find the main frequency components and the time of their occurrences. The calculated arrival time difference and known source to sensor distance were used to calculate the velocity of the excited AE wave. To identify available Lamb wave modes, the dispersion curve for a 3mm thick aluminium plate was studied. Dispersion curves were calculated using Vallen Dispersion software (release A2009.1027, Vallen System GmbH) [26]. The equation for linear source location as mentioned in literature [27] was used to calculate the velocity of the propagating waves.

$$L_1 + L_2 = D$$

$$L_1 = 0.5 * (D - \Delta t * c)$$

Equation 4.1

Here, D is the known distance between two transducers, Δt is the signal arrival time difference between transducers, c is the AE wave velocity, L_1 and L_2 are the distances from the two transducers to the source.

Figure 4.19 The initial 250 μs length of the data recorded (a) wave arrived at 1st thin film sensor around 43 μs (b) wave arrived at 2nd thin film sensor around 212 μs

The initial 250 μs length of the recorded data from both thin film sensors arranged in a linear fashion is shown in Figure 4.19. It is clearly indicated that the AE signal at the first sensor arrived at an earlier time than the signal at the second sensor. The reflections in the acquired signals were occurred but with small amplitudes than the simulated crack signals. Also, signal attenuation can easily be observed as the wave travels towards the second sensor. The signal arrival time difference (Δt) between the sensors was calculated using the cross-correlation method. Figure 4.20 represents the cross-correlation analysis for the full-length data recorded at both sensing nodes. It is observed that the cross-correlation of the two measurements was maximum at a lag equal to the delay of 338 data points which gave the Δt around 169 μs with 2 MHz of the sampling rate. By utilising Equation 4.1, the derived velocity was found around 3100 ms^{-1} .

Figure 4.20 The cross-correlation of the two measurements is maximum at a lag equal to the delay of 338 data points

The initial 250 μs length of the recorded data as shown in Figure 4.19 was considered for time-frequency analysis. The wavelet transforms (WT) tool was used to identify the main frequency components of the data with their time of occurrences. Figure 4.21 shows the spectrograms for both sensors.

Figure 4.21 Wavelet transform shows superimposed A_0 and S_0 group velocity-based dispersion curves after conversion to arrival times based on the propagation distance for (a) first sensor (0.10 m) (b) second sensor (0.62 m)

Both sensors have detected the signals with frequencies between 100 to 600 kHz with main frequency components at around 180 kHz. In Figure 4.21(a), the spectrogram for 1st sensor indicates that the acoustic wave was arrived at around 45 μs with frequencies between 100-200 kHz. For the second sensor, the wave was arrived at around 215 μs with frequencies between 100-200 kHz, as shown in Figure 4.21(b). Also, the reflection of acoustic waves from the edges of the specimen can also be seen in the spectrograms. To study the dominant Lamb wave modes, the group velocity dispersion curve was calculated as shown in Figure 4.22. The dispersion curve was superimposed on WT results in Figure 4.21 with modification by conversion of the group velocities to time by use of the 0.110m distance. The results demonstrate that the AE signals were strongly dominated by the zero-order flexural mode (A_0), as opposed to the symmetric mode (S_0). From both spectrograms, it was observed that the signal

arrival time difference (Δt) between the sensing nodes was found around 170 μs . Table 4.5 represents the Δt and c derived from the cross-correlation algorithm and wavelet transformation. The results derived from both methods were found in a close match.

Figure 4.22 Dispersion curve for 3 mm thick Al plate

Known source location m ($\pm 5mm$)	Δt (μs) calculated MATLAB	Velocity (ms^{-1})	Δt (μs) calculated WT	Velocity (ms^{-1})
0.110,0.0	169	3100	170	3000

Table 4.5 Δt and c for source location (0.11,0) m in Al plate specimen using experimental data

4.7 Experiments for triangulation source location

Acoustic emission source detection and localization was performed on a mild steel plate structure, the plate had dimensions of (1 x 1 x 0.003) m. An array of three AE sensors was arranged in a triangulation fashion to detect acoustic waves generated by simulated AE sources. For good acoustic coupling, the sensors were attached to the steel structure using vacuum grease as a couplant. A PicoScope-3000 series USB oscilloscope (Pico Technology Ltd) with four channels was used for data acquisition with a sampling rate of 1 MHz for 2 ms which allows 2000 data point acquisition, and an in-house developed AE prototype system was used for data acquisition.

The data were recorded from all three AE sensors when one of the received sensing signals exceeded the noise level set at 70 mV. The complete experimental setup to perform AE testing in lab is shown in Figure 4.23. Artificial AE sources for the tests were generated using ball drop method in an identical way as engendered for thin film devices repeatability tests.

Figure 4.23 Experimental setup for AE source location. In-house developed thin film AE sensors as a standalone sensing device were arranged in triangulation fashion. Each sensor connected to preamplifier and trigger block for acquiring simulated AE events

4.7.1 Acoustic emission testing using thin film AE sensors in triangulation fashion

Using an experimental setup as shown in Figure 4.23, the experiments were performed to detect and locate simulated AE sources in a triangulation fashion. The location for each of the thin film sensors with X & Y coordinates were mentioned in Table 4.6. The known source locations were mentioned in Table 4.7. At each source location, the ball drop tests were conducted five times and source location calculation was performed to estimate the distance vector error.

Sensing node	X- Coordinates	Y- Coordinates
S1	0 m	0 m
S2	1 m	0 m
S3	0.5 m	1 m

Table 4. 6 X and Y coordinates for positioned sensing nodes

Source location	X - Coordinate	Y - Coordinate
Source 1	0.49 m	0.01 m
Source 2	0.01 m	0.44 m
Source 3	0.49 m	0.89 m
Source 4	1 m	0.90 m

Table 4.7 X and Y coordinates for known source locations

In plate like structures Lamb waves are dominant, therefore it was advantageous to identify and study the presence of dominant Lamb wave modes in the acquired data further in detail. As an example, a ball drop test at the known location (0.01, 0.44) m was included and the time domain waveforms from all three sensors are shown in Figure 4.24. For this example, the distance from the known source location to the sensors S1, S2 and S3 were calculated 0.44, 1.09 and 0.75 m respectively. The stress waves first travelled and received at S1 as it was nearer to the emission source then waves arrived at S3 and S2 successively. The signals arrival time at each sensor was calculated using the Akaike information criterion (AIC) [28] algorithm, written in MATLAB, as shown in Appendix A. The calculated arrival time values of the transient signals at S1, S2 and S3 were found to be $t_1= 182$, $t_2= 400$ and $t_3= 292$ μs respectively.

Figure 4.24 Time domain waveforms using thin films AE sensors (a) S1, (b) S2 and (c) S3

After estimating the on-set time of the transient signals at each sensor, frequency domain analysis was carried out to study the dominant Lamb wave modes and their velocity.

The time domain data shown in Figure 4.24 were utilised to perform the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) using MATLAB platform (see Appendix A), the frequency spectra shown in Figure 4.25. It was observed that most frequency peaks were found between 40 to 160 kHz. However, in FFT results the time of occurrence of the frequency components was missing. To obtain main frequency components as a function of time, short time Fourier transform (STFT) and wavelet transform were carried out. The STFT was performed using the written algorithm in MATLAB (see Appendix A) and results were plotted in the linear scale, as shown in Figure 4.26. The wavelet transforms were calculated for the same signals using AGU Vallen Wavelet software (release A2009.1027, Vallen System GmbH, Icking Germany) [26], the spectrograms shown in Figure 4.27.

From spectrograms presented in Figure 4.26 and Figure 4.27, it was observed that waves with frequencies between 120 kHz and 100 kHz arrived initially. Afterwards, waves arrived with large variations in frequencies and gradual reduction was observed from 120 kHz to 40 kHz. The spectrograms showed maximum energy at approximately 80 kHz and 60 kHz. These two main frequency components were found in a good relationship with values seen in Fourier transform in Figure 4.25.

In addition to observing the frequencies of the first arrived Lamb wave modes, their arrival time values were also observed and compared. Table 4.8 shows the calculated signal on-set time at each sensing node using AIC, STFT and WT attempts.

	AIC	STFT	WT
Signal on-set time at S1 (μs)	182	178	180
Signal on-set time at S2 (μs)	400	398	400
Signal on-set time at S3 (μs)	292	290	300

Table 4.8 Calculated AE signal on-set time at each thin film transducer

Figure 4. 25 Fast Fourier transform for the data recorded by thin films AE sensors (a) S1, (b) S2 and (c) S3 for source location (0.01, 0.44) m

Figure 4.26 STFT spectrogram (linear scale) for the data recorded by thin films AE sensors (a) S1, (b) S2 and (c) S3 for source location (0.01, 0.44) m

Figure 4.27 Wavelet spectrograms (linear scale) for the data recorded by thin film AE sensors (a) S1, (b) S2 and (c) S3 for source location (0.01, 0.44) m with superimposed group velocity curves

As mentioned earlier, the available Lamb wave modes with corresponding velocities need to be known to locate the emission source in the plate structure. To investigate the present Lamb wave modes in recorded AE data, the theoretical Lamb wave group dispersion curves were calculated for a 3 mm thick steel plate using Vallen Dispersion software (release A2009.1027, Vallen System GmbH) [26], as shown in Figure 4.28. The curves were showing the variation in group velocities of different Lamb wave modes for frequency and thickness of the plate. Only lower order Lamb wave modes (symmetrical) S_0 and (asymmetrical) A_0 were presented here because no higher frequency waves were evident in the experimental results (higher frequency waves needed for higher modes).

Figure 4. 28 Calculated dispersion curves for 3 mm thick mild steel plate structure

Calculated frequency thickness products ($f \cdot d$) MHz-mm for the initially arrived waves were found between 0.30 and 0.36 MHz-mm, within this region, the S_0 mode became dispersive which indicated that this mode did not occur in the recorded data as the S_0 mode is non-dispersive [24]. Therefore, for this range of frequency thickness product, the group velocity of around 2570 ms^{-1} was seen for A_0 mode and found this mode dispersive in this region which is the fundamental characteristic of zero-order asymmetric mode.

To estimate the rest of the simulated AE source locations the same wave mode analyses method was utilised. The calculated signal arrival time values and velocity values of the first arrived Lamb wave modes were used to locate the source of emission. For the implementation of the trilateration technique, the derivations as mentioned in [25] were written in MATLAB and the algorithm was used for source location (see, Appendix A). Figure 4.29 shows a graphical representation of the trilateration results, the figure presented four known source locations with

the cross (blue in colour), the estimated source locations were represented with a circle (black in colour) and the sensor locations were represented with a plus (red in colour).

Figure 4.29 Triangulation source location in 3 mm thick steel plate using thin film AE sensors

4.7.2 Acoustic emission testing using UT-1000 AE sensors in triangulation fashion

Acoustic emission sensors UT-1000 from (Physical Acoustic Ltd) were benchmarked against in-house developed thin film AE sensors for simulated AE source detections and locations. The experimental setup was the same as shown in Figure 4.23, but this time UT-1000 sensors were coupled to the plate structure in a triangulation fashion. The sensor locations and each source location remained the same as mentioned in Table 4.6 and Table 4.7. For AE source simulation again ball drop method was used and at each location the tests were performed five times.

To benchmark with the thin film AE sensors, the AE data recorded from source location (0.01, 0.44) m using commercial AE sensors were included here and discussed further, the recorded time domain data from each sensing node is shown in Figure 4.30.

The time domain data from UT-1000 sensors showed that the influence of metal ball drop resulted in various transient signals. These bounces were also exhibited in the time domain plot from the thin film AE sensors in Figure 4.24 but with low energy and therefore not noticeable. This was due to the reduced sensitivity of the thin film AE sensors at low frequencies.

Figure 4.30 Time domain waveforms using UT-1000 AE sensors (a) S1, (b) S2 and (c) S3

The time domain data shown in Figure 4.30 were used for frequency domain analysis, the FFT tool was applied, and the results were shown in Figure 4.31. The results indicated that most of the frequency peaks occurred between 40 to 130 kHz, with some minor peaks between 150 and 200 kHz. From frequency domain analysis it was revealed that thin film AE sensors were more efficient to detect faster propagating wave components in comparison to the commercial wideband AE sensors. This might be due to the reason that the thin film elements have relatively good piezoelectric coefficients compared to the bulk PZT elements as discussed in [26]. In the next step, the STFT and WT were performed to obtain both time and frequency results.

From spectrograms presented in Figure 4.32 and Figure 4.33, it was noticed that waves with frequencies between 100 kHz and 130 kHz arrived initially. Afterwards, waves arrived with large variation in frequencies and a gradual decrease was observed from 140 kHz to 40 kHz, with maximum energy components occurring approximately 80 kHz and 60 kHz and found in good relationship with main frequency components found in Fourier transform, as shown in Figure 4.31.

The signals on-set time at each AE sensor were derived using AIC, STFT and WT approaches. Table 4.9 shows the comparison for signal on-set time at each AE sensor.

	AIC	STFT	WT
Signal on-set time at S1 (μs)	185	180	190
Signal on-set time at S2 (μs)	410	415	405
Signal on-set time at S3 (μs)	300	295	290

Table 4.9 Calculated AE signal on-set time at each UT-1000 sensor using three different methods

Figure 4.31 Fast Fourier transform for the data recorded by UT-1000 AE sensors (a) S1, (b) S2 and (c) S3 for source location (0.01, 0.44) m

Figure 4.32 STFT spectrogram (linear scale) for the data recorded by UT-1000 AE sensors (a) S1, (b) S2 and (c) S3 for source location (0.01, 0.44) m

Figure 4.33 Wavelet spectrograms (linear scale) for the data recorded by UT-1000 AE sensors (a) S1, (b) S2 and (c) S3 for source location (0.01, 0.44) m with superimposed group velocity curves

To locate the emission sources in the steel plate, the velocity of the initially arrived Lamb wave mode need to be known. From the results, it was found that the initial waves arrived with the main frequencies between 100 and 130 kHz, which gave the frequency thickness products ($f \cdot d$) between 0.3 and 0.39 MHz-mm for the 3 mm steel plate. Figure 4.28 revealed that within this range the zero-order symmetrical Lamb wave mode S_0 became dispersive, hence the first arrived signals were not considered the symmetric Lamb wave mode. Therefore, the group velocity of around 2500 ms^{-1} was seen for A_0 mode and found this mode dispersive in this region which is the fundamental characteristic of zero-order asymmetric mode.

Figure 4.34 Triangulation source location in 3 mm thick steel plate using UT-1000 AE sensors

The waveforms from other sources were also characterized using the same post-processing steps. Figure 4.34 shows a graphical representation of the trilateration results, the figure presented four known source locations with the cross (blue in colour), the estimated source locations were represented with a circle (black in colour) and the sensor locations were represented with a plus (red in colour).

4.8 Conclusions

Thin film elements were sputtered with optimised parameters using DC sputtering system. The deposited films were characterised for piezoelectric applications using SEM and XRD methods the results suggested c-axis oriented crystal structure which is the main requirement for manufacturing the AE sensing devices.

In this work the films were deposited on different substrate thicknesses, the measured S_{11} parameter suggested that the thickness mode resonances frequency gradually decreased as the thickness of the substrate increased. Also, it was noticed that reflection losses increased as the thickness of the substrate increased because most of the transmitted signal bounced inside the thick substrate and less energy transmitted to the active element.

For this research work, standalone AE sensing devices were developed using rigid assembly, and the approach of using flexible substrate contributed not much from a design perspective. But in this feasibility study, the main aim was to prove the concept that thin film devices are suitable to detect AE events. The outcomes of this feasibility study will help to move one step forward to utilise the flexibility feature of the substrate and help to utilise them for complex geometries.

The developed devices were characterised using impedance versus frequency curves. Impedance sweeps were carried out for both thin films and commercial AE sensing devices. ZnO thin film devices showed capacitive response from 0.1-1 MHz, on the other hand, the commercial AE sensing devices indicated both lateral and longitudinal modes from 0.1-1 MHz, associated with the characteristics of the active element dimensions used in these devices.

The repeatability for the developed thin film sensing devices was analysed. The small experiment was performed using a metal plate specimen, the sensing device was coupled to the surface of the plate and consecutive 10-AE events were generated using ball drop test. The mean peak amplitude of the 10 shots was found 0.3 V with two- standard deviations of 0.03 V which suggested that the spread of the data is 10-times smaller than the mean value.

The time domain waveforms acquired using commercial AE sensors in Figure 4.30 suggested that the signal generated by the impact of the metal ball drop resulted in several transient signals. On the other hand, these bounces were not observed in the time domain data acquired using the thin film sensors in Figure 4.24. This was due to the inadequate sensitivity of the thin

film device coupled with a low signal to noise ratio. The output signal from the thin film device shows an amplitude four times smaller than that from the commercial sensor. It was noticed that the thin film sensors detected the AE events before the UT-1000 sensor. PZT material has high piezoelectric coefficient d_{31} (27-274 pC/N) [29] but show low sensing response due to its higher dielectric constant. This may be possible that the thin film piezoelectric devices have different piezoelectric properties.

Further to the testing for AE events detection at room temperature, in the next chapter the thin film devices were developed for the detection of AE events at ambient temperatures. The thin-film transducers were small and high-temperature resistant in the 100-300°C range.

Actual source location	Calculated source location - 1st ball drop	Calculated source location - 2nd ball drop	Calculated source location - 3rd ball drop	Calculated source location - 4th ball drop	Calculated source location - 5th ball drop	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean distance vector error $\sqrt{(x_{mean} - x_{actual})^2 + (y_{mean} - y_{actual})^2}$
(0.49,0.01) m	(0.48,0.0075) m	(0.49,0.01) m	(0.49,0.01) m	(0.49,0.0075) m	(0.5,0.01) m	(0.49,0.009) m	(0.007,0.001) m	0.0015 m
(0.01,0.44) m	(0.01,0.44) m	(0.0014,0.45) m	(0.005,0.45) m	(0.007,0.44) m	(0.006,0.45) m	(0.007,0.44) m	(0.005,0.005) m	0.007 m
(0.49,0.89) m	(0.5,0.88) m	(0.5,0.88) m	(0.49,0.87) m	(0.5,0.87) m	(0.49,0.89) m	(0.496,0.88) m	(0.005,0.01) m	0.013 m
(1.0,0.90) m	(1.0,0.91) m	(0.988,0.89) m	(1.0,0.86) m	(1.0,0.91) m	(0.983,0.89) m	(0.99,0.89) m	(0.009,0.01) m	0.012 m

Table 4. 10 AE source location data summary using ZnO thin films AE sensors

Actual source location	Calculated source location - 1st ball drop	Calculated source location - 2nd ball drop	Calculated source location - 3rd ball drop	Calculated source location - 4th ball drop	Calculated source location - 5th ball drop	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean distance vector error $\sqrt{(x_{mean} - x_{actual})^2 + (y_{mean} - y_{actual})^2}$
(0.49,0.01) m	(0.52,0.03) m	(0.5,0.04) m	(0.52,0.01) m	(0.5,0.03) m	(0.51,0.0075) m	(0.51,0.02) m	(0.01,0.01) m	0.024 m
(0.01,0.44) m	(0.018,0.46) m	(0.032,0.47) m	(0.05,0.43) m	(0.05,0.43) m	(0.038,0.446) m	(0.04,0.45) m	(0.01,0.01) m	0.03 m
(0.49,0.89) m	(0.55,0.92) m	(0.53,0.89) m	(0.5,0.91) m	(0.49,0.91) m	(0.5,0.9) m	(0.51,0.90) m	(0.02,0.01) m	0.022 m
(1.0,0.90) m	(1.01,0.91) m	(1.02,0.92) m	(0.95,0.9) m	(1.01,0.94) m	(0.99,0.93) m	(0.99,0.92) m	(0.03,0.02) m	0.02 m

Table 4. 11 AE source location data summary using commercial UT-1000 AE sensors

4.9 References

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CHAPTER 5

High temperature acoustic emission testing using zinc oxide thin film broadband AE testing

5.1 Introduction

The main aim of this chapter is to investigate the functionality of zinc oxide (ZnO) thin film broadband sensors at elevated temperatures up to 300°C. This chapter is covered the following aspects of the high temperature testing: (i) Annealing tests for 6µm thin film sputtered on soft aluminium (Al) foil substrate of 50µm. (ii) Develop and characterise the thin films sensors for acoustic emissions (AE) testing at room and elevated temperatures. (iii) In the lab environment, characterise the performance of thin film sensors for detecting the simulated AE events from room temperature up to 300°C in the metal plate structure.

5.2 Study of post-annealing treatment for ZnO thin films

The properties of the ZnO thin films such as structural strength and piezoelectric performance are considerably affected due to the large film stress which is mainly found in a few microns of sputtered films structures, [1, 2]. Post-annealing method is commonly used to reduce the film stress for the as-deposited films, [3, 4]. In this chapter the post-annealing treatment for ZnO thin film elements was carried out, the temperature ranges from 100-500 °C. An example image of the thin film elements was presented in chapter 4 (Figure 4.6). The films were annealed at elevated temperatures for one hour in a furnace (CTF 11/140, Serial No. 10/87/1387, Carbolite Gero Ltd, UK).

5.2.1 Structure analysis for ZnO thin films

Structural analysis for as deposited and post-annealed ZnO thin film elements was carried out using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Hitachi S4100) and crystal orientation was analysed using X-ray diffraction (XRD, Siemens D5000 Cu K α , 40 kV/30 mA).

The magnified SEM cross-sectional view of the as-deposited ZnO film element is shown in Figure 5.1(a). The large film stress is observed due to the curved deformation of 50 μ m Al foil after film sputtering (this is one of the challenges of using a flexible substrate which make film characterisation more complex). The as-deposited film shows observable column structure on the foil which is crucial for the film to act as a piezoelectric material, as discussed in literature the [5]. The cross-sectional view for the post-annealed ZnO film elements is shown in Figure 5.1 (b-f), it is observed that as the annealing temperature increases the film structure becomes more compact columnar without obvious cracking and delamination which indicates that the post-annealing method is an aid to minimize the film stress.

The crystal structure of the ZnO thin films was investigated using X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements. The diffraction angle was set between 20 & 60 degrees with 1 scan (count) per second at 0.2° increments. Figure 5.2 shows XRD spectra for the as deposited and post-annealed samples of ZnO thin films on Al foil substrate. The as-deposited film as shown in Figure 5.2 (a) has two indicating peaks, the first intense peak (002) related to ZnO while the weaker one (200) related to aluminium. These peaks measurements and the values of 2 θ are in good agreement with the results reported in the literatures [6-8]. The post-annealing treatment at 100 °C and above shows that the (002) ZnO peaks are more prominent over other peaks. It is observed from the peak profile analysis that, in comparison to the as-deposited films, the post-annealed films treated specially at 400 °C and above showed a noticeable high intensity count and less peak broadening, which indicates that the post annealing treatment encourages the strong ZnO film texture with C-axis orientation. With the XRD profiles of the as deposited and post annealed ZnO films, the crystallites size may be estimated by using Scherrer's formula [8,9]:

$$D = \frac{0.9\lambda}{B\cos\theta}$$

Equation 5. 1

Where D is the crystallite size, λ is the wavelength of Cu K α radiation, B is full width half maximum (FWHM) of the (0002) ZnO peak and θ is the Bragg's angle. Table 5.1 includes the crystallite size calculated using the Scherrer equation for the heat-treated sample from room temperature to 500 °C.

Figure 5.1 SEM images of approximately 6 μm thin ZnO film on 50 μm thick Al foil substrate, (a) cross-section of as-deposited film, (b) cross-section of 100 °C annealed film, (c) cross-section of 200 °C annealed film, (d) cross-section of 300 °C annealed film, (e) cross-section of 400 °C annealed film and (f) cross-section of 500 °C annealed film

Figure 5.2 XRD peak profiles for ZnO element at (a) as deposited, (b) 100 °C, (c) 200 °C, (d) 300 °C, (e) 400 °C, (f) 500 °C.

Temperature (degree Celsius)	Calculated Particle size (nm)	Predicted Particle size (nm)
25	16.1157	15.184
100	20.72	18.934
200	23.03	23.934
300	24.7	28.934
400	34.55	33.934
500	41.46	38.934

Table 5.1 Crystallite sizes from 25 to 500 °C. The table included calculated and predicted grain size at elevated temperature

At each elevated temperature single XRD measurement was taken, and error estimation was performed for the data points. Statistical analysis was carried out, as shown in Figure 5.3, the trendline was plotted including the regression equation. A standard error of estimation (SEE) was calculated to measure the dispersion of the observed values around the line of regression. Equation 5.2 was utilised for calculating SEE, from the calculation the standard estimation of the error was found ± 3.69 nm. The graph in Figure 5.3 also revealed that the SEE can be

interpreted as the standard deviation in the sense that with normal distribution for prediction errors, 83% of the crystallite size fell within a SEE of ± 3.69 nm.

$$SEE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=0}^N (Y - Y')^2}{N - 2}}$$

Equation 5. 2

Here,

Y , representing actual experimental grain sizes at elevated temperatures calculated using Equation 6.1.

Y' , representing predicted grain sizes calculated using regression equation.

N , representing total number of data points.

Figure 5.3 The graph indicated the gradual increment in grain size as the annealing temperature incremented

5.2.2 Piezoelectric analysis for ZnO thin films

To study the piezoelectric properties for the as deposited and post-annealed thin films samples, the reflection loss (S_{11}) measurements were carried out. The measured S_{11} spectra are shown in Figure 5.4. From the inset, it is shown that for as deposited and the post-annealed ZnO/Al foil samples the first resonance peaks occurred at approximately 54 MHz. The ringing effect was observed due to the longitudinal waves bouncing inside the foil substrate. The reflection loss for the as-deposited sample and the samples annealed up to 200 °C was measured at around -0.25 dB, and this suggested less energy loss due to the presence of fewer discontinuities within the structure of the ZnO/Al foil sample. This reflection loss gradually decreased with the increase in annealing temperatures from 300-500 °C.

Figure 5.4 Measured reflection loss for as deposited and post-annealed samples, S_{11} for ZnO (6 μm)/ Al foil (50 μm) thin film devices as a function of frequency. It shows multiple resonances in the Al foil substrate. The inset shows first resonance peaks for as de deposited and post-annealed samples

5.3 High temperature thin films AE sensors

5.3.1 Design and fabrication

The design and development of high temperature sensors is a real challenge that demands different techniques and methods to make sensing devices more robust for harsh environments. After investigating post-annealed ZnO thin films samples, the next stage was to fabricate the sensing devices.

Relative to the design for room temperature testing, as discussed in chapter 4, a conductive high temperature carbon paste PELCO® from (agar scientific) was used as a back face electrode. To provide mechanical support to the internal assembly of the sensing device and avoid punctures in the foil substrate, zirconia cement (Resbond 940, Cotronics Corp) was used as backing support. Also, the zirconia-based cement was used to minimize the thermal conductivity as discussed and used in the literature [10].

Figure 5.5 (a) back face electrode using conductive carbon paste, (b) added zirconia-based cement to reduce thermal effects and (c) Complete thin film AE sensor assembly with copper case and SMA connector

To identify the robustness of three in-house developed AE sensing devices, one of the sensing devices was heated on the hot plate up to 500 °C before conducting any test and it was found that the assembly of the device was not robust/heat resistive and not withstand at such a high temperature. This physical deterioration to the assembly limits the temperature range up to 300 °C for AE testing and suggested that the design of the assembly required more refinement.

Figure 5.6 The in-house developed AE sensing device for high temperature testing. The device heated on the hot plate at 500 °C, the physical damage to the assembly can be seen clearly in both images

5.3.2 Bespoke thin films AE sensors electrical properties characterization

5.3.2.1 Using Impedance analyser

In Figure 5.7(a), it can be observed that the spectrum exhibits single mechanical vibration in the measured frequency ranges (0-110 MHz). The graphical representation shows the single thickness mode resonant frequency for thin film sensor occurred at approximately 54 MHz which gives the element thickness of around 56 μm with the velocity of 6026 ms^{-1} for zinc oxide, the resultant thickness of the element indicates that the thin film considered the substrate thickness into account while generating the resonant mode and the ringing is predictable at higher frequencies due to the bouncing of longitudinal acoustic waves inside the substrate.

The in-house developed thin film sensors were further characterized within the low frequency spectrum (0-10 MHz). Figure 5.7(b) shows the graph with flat impedance magnitude response and negative phase values for selected wide frequency range, as expected from thin film sensor, the same observations were made in literature [11].

Figure 5.7 Frequency sweep vs impedance and phase for the bespoke thin film AE sensor, (a) 1-110 MHz and (b) 1-10 MHz

5.3.2.2 Using Network analyser

The measured reflection loss parameters S_{11} as a function of frequency is presented in Figure 5.8. From the inset in the graph low reflection loss was observed for frequency ranges 0-10 MHz. The reflection loss axis indicated that the transducer under test is the passive device and absorbed some of the incident signal, which indicating a lossy behaviour.

Figure 5.8 Measured reflection loss, S_{11} of ZnO ($6\ \mu\text{m}$)/Al foil ($50\ \mu\text{m}$) thin film sensor as a function of frequency. It shows multiple resonances in the Al foil substrate. The inset in the graph indicating first thickness mode resonance at approximately 54 MHz

5.4 Experimental setup and testing in Lab environment

For the experiments, the test specimen had a dimension of 0.3 m by 0.15 m and a thickness of 6 mm. The data acquisition system was used the PICOscope-3000 series with four channels from (Pico Technology Ltd). The data were acquired at a sampling frequency of 2 MHz for 1 ms duration which allows acquisition of 2000 data points. The thin film sensor was held using magnetic clamps and high temperature couplant EchoTerm™ Extreme from (ECHO ultrasonics) was applied to couple the bespoke AE sensors to test plate for good acoustic coupling. The given operating range for the couplant is -40 to $675\ ^\circ\text{C}$ with auto ignition temperature greater than $704\ ^\circ\text{C}$. For safety reasons the selected couplant was used to take measurements from 25 to $300\ ^\circ\text{C}$. Initially, the experiments were conducted at room temperature and data were recorded for reference with high temperature test results.

Figure 5.9 Schematic presents an arrangement of the thin film sensor and an artificial AE event on the test specimen

For high temperature tests, a hot plate was used for heating the test specimen at elevated temperatures in the air. The mild steel test specimen assembled with the thin film sensor was placed at the hot plate. To avoid damage to the coaxial cables connecting the thin film sensor with the AE system, they were held away from the hot plate using the clamping stands, as shown in Figure 5.10. The hot plate heated up to 300 °C by 10 °C increments starting from room temperature, it was heated 25 °C above for each target temperature to avoid cooling during the measurements. To minimize the electromagnetic interference during AE measurements, the hot plate was switched-off once the required temperature was achieved. Before unplugging the hot plate, 15 minutes was allowed for the thin film sensor to stay above the targeted temperatures and absorbed enough heat, this time limit was used to investigate the design limitations for the assembly of the thin film sensor.

Figure 5.10 Acoustic emission based high temperature AE testing setup using the ZnO thin film sensors

5.5 Results and discussion

5.5.1 Acoustic emission source detection at room temperature

As an example, one of the ball drop tests at known source location is included here, initial 250 μs time domain data with the wavelet analysis is shown in Figure 5.11.

Figure 5.11 A representative time-domain plot with wavelet analysis for the data recorded at room temperature for source location (50) mm with superimposed group velocity curves

The time of flight was found approximately 17 μs which suggested the wave velocity of 2941.2 ms^{-1} was calculated using the known distance of 50 mm between the thin film sensor and the source. The wavelet transform (WT) tool was used to obtain corresponding time and frequency representation. The wavelet analyses were done using AGU Vallen Wavelet software (release A2009.1027, Vallen System GmbH, Icking Germany) [11], the spectrogram suggested that the main frequency component of 120 kHz occurred at 17 μs .

To investigate the present Lamb wave modes in recorded AE data, the theoretical group velocities dispersion curves were produced for a 6 mm thick steel plate using Vallen Dispersion software (release A2009.1027, Vallen System GmbH) [11], as shown in Figure 5.12. The group velocity curves suggested that the initial excitation was triggered by the A₀ mode with the group velocity around 3028 ms^{-1} . This theoretical value was found close to the velocity value measured for arrived AE wave.

Figure 5.12 Lamb wave group velocity dispersion curves of the 6mm thick steel plate

5.5.2 Acoustic emission source detection at 100, 200 and 300°C temperatures

The experiments were performed to examine the performance of the thin film sensor at elevated temperatures. The simulated AE events were recorded for each temperature increment of 100 °C. As an example, one of the ball drop tests at a known source location is included here and the recorded waveform at 100, 200 and 300 °C are shown in Figure 5.13.

The time domain data and spectrogram for the AE event that occurred at 100 °C show no significant difference relative to the reference data. The recorded AE data at 200 °C shows that the sensor was excited at around 21 μs with the wave velocity measured around 2381 ms^{-1} . The amplitude of the time domain signal marginally decreased (0.5 mV). The spectrogram suggested that the initial AE wave arrived 5 μs later in time relative to the reference data with the frequency component of 40 kHz occurring at 21 μs . The late arriving mode with lower frequency component is associated with the dispersive A_0 mode with the group velocity of around 2399 ms^{-1} . Both theoretical and measured velocities values were in a good match.

Time domain data recorded at 300 °C, the occurrence of the AE event suggested that as the temperature increases velocity decreases. Also, the amplitude of the recorded data attenuated further relative to the reference data. The frequency component of 25 kHz occurred at 25 μs with the measured velocity of 2000 ms^{-1} . The spectrogram shows a similar characteristic behaviour of the arriving mode. The group velocity dispersion curves revealed that the initially arrived mode was associated with the dispersive A_0 mode with the group velocity of around 2082 ms^{-1} . Again, both theoretical and measured velocities indicated marginal differences.

Figure 5.13 Representative time-domain plots of the in-house developed thin film sensor. Data recorded at (a) 100 °C, (b) 200 °C and (c) 300 °C. For source location (50) mm with superimposed group velocity curves

5.6 Conclusions

The conclusion from post-annealing treatment revealed the improved reflection loss values in comparison to the as-deposited sample. The c-axis orientation of the deposited film for as-deposited and post-annealed samples indicated that the annealing treatment is helpful to reduce the structural discontinuities which may cause due to cracks and delamination.

For high temperature testing, the time domain data indicated the velocity of the acoustic waves was decreased gradually with the increment in temperature, theoretical and experimental results were presented to show that using Lamb waves is an effective way of detecting AE events. The poor acoustic coupling and degradation of the sensor's assembly for high temperature tests would be the possible reasons for signal attenuation.

Also, this deterioration of the signal quality at high temperatures was considered due to the difference in the coefficient of the thermal expansions (CTEs) of the ZnO and Al foil and heat induced surface-oxidation of Al foil substrate. The large differences in the CTEs might be the cause to initiate discontinuities in the structure of the ZnO thin films.

5.7 References

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CHAPTER 6

Summary and Future work

6.1 Conclusion

This section concludes the findings of the work carried out throughout the study. The main aim of this work was to fabricate the broadband zinc oxide (ZnO) thin film sensors for AE events detection as a proof of concept.

This work shows the successful development and implementation of the AE prototype system. The system consists of two main blocks, first block performed signal conditioning and the second block was used for the logical triggering of the data acquisition system to record AE events. Signals from the sensing nodes were amplified with a fixed gain of approximately ~55 dB and filtered using a bandpass filter with a -3dB bandwidth of ~0.6 MHz, these sensing signals were then compared to user defined reference voltage for the logical triggering of the data acquisition system. This trigger approach helps to minimize the loss of meaningful data which is often lost due to AE wave attenuation. Also, this approach helps to manage memory space for the recorded AE data because the AE events contain a large amount of data which take up large memory space especially in the case of continuous monitoring.

In this work, zinc oxide thin films were sputtered on aluminium foils substrate of different thicknesses using the optimised parameters as mentioned in Table 4.1. During sputtering the masking technique was used which aids to sputter 8 mm diameter ZnO thin film elements with approximately 6 μm thickness in a fashion of 6 rows and 4 columns matrix on the substrates. The film structure and crystal orientation were investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscope (SEM). From SEM the film stress was observed due to the curved deformation of Al foil substrates with sputtered ZnO film was shown column structure. The XRD analysis indicated high intensity peak at 2θ of approximately 34.4° which associated with ZnO (002) crystal orientation with the c-axis normal to foil substrate.

Electrical characteristics of the ZnO thin films devices were analysed using the reflection coefficient (S_{11}) using a specially designed test fixture for the measurements. Also, One-dimensional modelling (ODM) was used to study the S_{11} measurements, and a comparison was made for the experimental and simulated S_{11} spectra. From the results, it was concluded that

the reverberation phenomenon occurred due to the bouncing of longitudinal waves inside the substrate. It was also noticed that with the increased substrate thickness the reverberations occurred more quickly due to increased wavelength; the resonance frequency decreased gradually from 53 to 36 and 28 MHz as the substrate thickness increased from 50 to 75 & 100 μm respectively. It was observed that with increased substrate thickness the reflection loss values were increased because most of the transmitted signal bounced inside the thick substrate rather than inserted into the device under test.

After completing the fabrication stages for three sensing devices, the electrical properties of the sensors were characterized using an impedance analyser for the frequency range 0-1 MHz which was well below the resonance frequency (approximately 54 MHz) of the thin film sensor. For the selected frequency range, the sensor response was found flat, capacitance-type. This response of the thin film AE sensors within low frequency regime made them appropriate for the characterization of the acoustic emission signal properties for wide frequency spectrum but the effectiveness of the sensor decreased when sensing the low energy acoustic waves due to the damping effect. For the benchmarking purpose, the electrical properties for the commercial AE sensor UT-1000 (Datasheet included in Appendix C) were also characterized and found that the sensor response was not flat within the frequency range of interest it would show good sensing for low energy acoustic waves. The thin film device was tested for repeatability performance, one of the sensing devices coupled to the mild steel plate and 10 consecutive ball drop shots were recorded. Statistical analysis suggested good repeatability performance with a mean amplitude of $(0.3 \pm 0.03 \text{ V})$

To prove the sensing ability of the in-house developed thin film AE sensors, they were utilised to examine the aluminium and mild steel plate structures in integration with the in-house developed AE prototype system. The standalone thin film AE sensors were arranged in linear and triangulation patterns to detect the simulated AE sources. For the simulated AE source, the pencil lead break and ball drop tests were performed at known locations. The commercial AE sensors UT-1000 were coupled to the steel plate structure in a triangulation fashion for AE tests benchmarking.

The recorded data from in-house and commercial AE sensors were analysed using a waveform-based approach. For arrival time estimation the AIC algorithm and cross-correlation algorithm were selected. For frequency domain analysis main consideration was given to STFT and WT to identify the main frequency components with their time of occurrences. From the analysis,

it was found that the in-house developed thin film-based AE sensors were equally capable of sensing AE waves like UT-1000 AE sensors. Both types of sensors had detected only lower order asymmetrical Lamb wave mode A_0 which indicated the on-surface displacement characteristics of the simulated AE source. For estimating the known AE source location, the thin film AE sensors showed minimum distance vector error in comparison with commercial AE sensors (UT-1000), which indicates the good piezoelectric properties (e.g., d_{31}) of the thin film elements.

The functionality of ZnO thin film sensors was evaluated for high temperature testing. Initially, the post-annealing treatment was performed (100-500 °C) for 6 μm thin ZnO film sputtered on soft aluminium (Al) foil substrate of 50 μm . The thin film structure and crystal orientation were investigated using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. From SEM, it was revealed that as the annealing temperature increased the film structure became more compact columnar without obvious cracking and delamination which indicates that the post-annealing method is an aid to minimize the film stress. The XRD analysis indicated that in comparison to the as-deposited ZnO films, the post-annealed films have shown high intensity count and less broadening in the peaks, which indicated that the post annealing treatment encourages the strong ZnO film texture with C-axis orientation.

Electrical properties for the post annealed samples were characterized using (S_{11}) measurements. It was observed that the as deposited and annealed samples up to 300 °C indicated more reflection loss due to the possible presence of discontinuities within the structure of the ZnO/Al foil sample. With the post-annealed treatment greater than 300 °C, the measured reflection loss values were decreased, which signifies that the post-annealing for the thin films is helpful to reduce the structural discontinuities due to cracks and delamination.

The thin films AE sensors were fabricated using a conductive high temperature carbon paste PELCO® from (agar scientific) and zirconia cement (Resbond 940, Cotronics Corp), data sheets included in Appendix C. The electrical properties of the bespoke thin film AE sensors were characterized using an impedance analyser and network analyser. The resonance frequency for the sensors was found approximately 54 MHz. It was found that for the frequency range of interest from (0-1 MHz) the sensors indicated capacitive-type response.

The experiments were conducted for temperatures from 25-300 °C to examine the plate like structure and analyse the design strength of the bespoke thin film sensors. For the experiment

high temperature couplant EchoTerm™ Extreme from (ECHO ultrasonics, the datasheet included in Appendix C) was selected. Ball drop tests were carried out to simulate AE source and recorded data were used to characterize dominant Lamb wave modes, the velocity of the modes and approximate source location. The results from the experiments were found encouraging, the thin film sensors were performed well at elevated temperatures and showed the capability of AE signals detection. The post-processing of the data revealed the sensor was activated due to the presence of zero-order antisymmetric Lamb wave mode.

The acquired data suggested that the velocity of the acoustic waves decreased gradually as the temperature increased. The accelerated deterioration of the signal amplitudes with increase in temperature may be attributed due to the difference in the coefficients of thermal expansions (CTE) of the ZnO thin film sensor and the test specimen. The acoustic coupling at high temperatures is another main factor for signal attenuation. The poor acoustic coupling and sensor assembly deterioration at high temperature led to reducing signal strength.

6.2 Future Work

Key points which can be covered as further work to enhance the aims and objectives of this research work and make it more adoptable in industrial environment with minimum efforts are:

- This research work has the potential to adopt commercially, but its need to be organised in representable form. The in-house developed AE prototype system needs to be adjusted in a small assembly with a data acquisition system in the same assembly, required necessary wiring arrangements and user guide to operate the whole system for AE testing. Required graphical user interface either in MATLAB or LabVIEW to record the data and perform further analysis.
- In this research work all the tests were carried out in a lab environment using simulated AE sources which were found quite like the real AE events, it is good to perform testing in a real environment for real time AE events detection. This opportunity gives more confidence about the performance of developed AE system, bespoke thin film AE sensors and the approaches used for post-processing of the data.
- In this work, the plate structures made of different metals (Aluminium and mild steel) were examined. It will be useful to examine pipe/cylindrical geometries.

- It will be valuable if these AE sensors will be utilised to detect AE events in composites.
- Instead of fabricating standalone AE sensing devices, the ZnO/Al foil elements can be utilised without any rigid assembly. This way we can utilise the maximum benefits of a flexible substrate and miniaturize the design of the sensing elements, especially when examining the geometries with curve shapes.
- High temperature testing at an elevated temperature greater than 300°C can be achieved by simply sputter the ZnO thin film directly onto the test samples. This method may not be found trivial for large test samples due to the limitation of the sputtering system, but alternative ways could be investigated. The direct thin film sputtering on the test sample will overcome the general problems associated with high temperature testing included: couplant temperature limitation and sensor assembly strength to survive in a harsh environment.
- Find different ways to design and develop ZnO thin film AE sensors, which make them more robust and representable.
- Investigate new materials for thin film sputtering which can be used as a piezoelectric material for AE sensors and suitable for high temperature AE testing, e.g., Aluminium Nitride (AlN). Investigate other thin film sputtering techniques, e.g., CVD and IAD.

Appendices

Appendix A

Arduino Uno coding for Logical trigger:

```
const int OutPin = 12; // output connected to digital pin 12
const int knockSensor1 = A0; // the piezo is connected to analog pin 0
const int knockSensor2 = A1; // the piezo is connected to analog pin 1
const int knockSensor3 = A2; // the piezo is connected to analog pin 2
const int threshold = 0.07*(5/1023); // threshold value to decide when the detected sound is a
knock or not
```

```
// these variables will change:
```

```
int sensorReading1 = 0; // variable to store the value read from the sensor1 pin
int sensorReading2 = 0; // variable to store the value read from the sensor2 pin
int sensorReading3 = 0; // variable to store the value read from the sensor3 pin
int OutPinstate=LOW;
```

```
void setup() {
```

```
  pinMode(OutPin, OUTPUT); // declare the pin 12 as OUTPUT
  Serial.begin(9600); // use the serial port
```

```
}
```

```
void loop() {
```

```
  // read the sensor and store it in the variable sensorReading1:
```

```
  sensorReading1 = analogRead(knockSensor1);
```

```
  sensorReading2 = analogRead(knockSensor2);
```

```
  sensorReading3 = analogRead(knockSensor3);
```

```
  // if any sensor reading is greater than the threshold:
```

```
  if ( (sensorReading1 >= threshold || sensorReading2 >= threshold ) || (sensorReading1 >=
threshold || sensorReading3 >= threshold ) ) {
```

```
    // toggle the status of the OutPin:
```

```
    OutPinstate = HIGH;
```

```
    digitalWrite(OutPin, OutPinstate);
```

```
    delay(8000);
```

```
    digitalWrite(OutPin, LOW);
```

```
  }
```

```
  else{
```

```
    OutPinstate=LOW;
```

```
    digitalWrite(OutPin, OutPinstate);
```

```
  }
```

```
}
```

Coding for on-set time calculation using AIC picker method:

```
k=detrend(B);p=detrend(C);q=detrend(D);
k1=k(1:1200);p1=p(1:1200);q1=q(1:1200);
t=(1:length(k1))*1e-6;t=t';
K1=[t,k1];P1=[t,p1];Q1=[t,q1];
H=abs(hilbert(k1))/abs(max(hilbert(k1)));
figure,plot (H);
th=0.2;
ix = find(H>th,1);
y=ix+100;
Rw=K1(1:y);
Tw=size(Rw);
c=zeros(Tw);
for i=1:Tw(1)
    z(i,1)=i*log(var(Rw(1:i)))+(Tw(1)-i-1)*log(var(Rw((i+1):Tw(1))));
    c(i,1)=z(i,1);
end
[ymin, yi] = min(c(2:y));
t1=K1(yi,1);
H=abs(hilbert(p1))/abs(max(hilbert(p1)));
figure,plot (H);
th=0.5;
ix = find(H>th,1);
y=ix+100;
Rw=p1(1:y);

Tw=size(Rw);
c=zeros(Tw);
for i=1:Tw(1)
    z(i,1)=i*log(var(Rw(1:i)))+(Tw(1)-i-1)*log(var(Rw((i+1):Tw(1))));
    c(i,1)=z(i,1);
end
[ymin, yi] = min(c(2:y));
t2=P1(yi,1);
H=abs(hilbert(q1))/abs(max(hilbert(q1)));
figure,plot (H);
th=0.5;
ix = find(H>th,1);
y=ix+100;
Rw=q1(1:y);
Tw=size(Rw);
c=zeros(Tw);
```

```

for i=1:Tw(1)
    z(i,1)=i*log(var(Rw(1:i)))+(Tw(1)-i-1)*log(var(Rw((i+1):Tw(1))));
    c(i,1)=z(i,1);
end
[ymin, yi] = min(c(2:y));
t3=Q1(yi,1);

```

Coding for Fast Fourier Transform:

```

l=length(k1);
fs=1.0e6;
nfft=2^nextpow2(l);
W=fft(k1,nfft)/l;
f=fs/2*linspace(0,1,nfft/2+1);
figure,plot(f,2*abs(W(1:nfft/2+1)));
[A1, I1]= max(abs(W));

```

```

l1=length(p1);
fs=1.0e6;
nfft=2^nextpow2(l1);
X=fft(p1,nfft)/l1;
f=fs/2*linspace(0,1,nfft/2+1);
figure,plot(f,2*abs(X(1:nfft/2+1)));
[A2, I2]= max(abs(X));

```

```

l2=length(q1);
fs=1.0e6;
nfft=2^nextpow2(l2);
Y=fft(q1,nfft)/l2;
f=fs/2*linspace(0,1,nfft/2+1);
figure,plot(f,2*abs(Y(1:nfft/2+1)));
[A3,I3]=max(abs(Y));

```

Coding for Short Fourier Transform:

```
fs = 1.0e6;
t=(0:length(k1)-1)*6e-7;t=t';
level = 6;
figure;
window = hanning(windowsize);
nfft = windowsize;
noverlap = windowsize-1;
[S,F,T] = spectrogram(B>window,noverlap,nfft,fs);
imagesc(T,F,log10(abs(S)))
set(gca,'YDir','Normal')
xlabel('Time (ms)')
ylabel('Freq (kHz)')
```

```
fs = 1.0e6;
t=(0:length(p1)-1)*6e-7;t=t';
level = 6;
figure;
window = hanning(windowsize);
nfft = windowsize;
noverlap = windowsize-1;
[S,F,T] = spectrogram(B>window,noverlap,nfft,fs);
imagesc(T,F,log10(abs(S)))
set(gca,'YDir','Normal')
xlabel('Time (ms)')
ylabel('Freq (kHz)')
```

```
fs = 1.0e6;
t=(0:length(q1)-1)*6e-7;t=t';
level = 6;
figure;
window = hanning(windowsize);
nfft = windowsize;
noverlap = windowsize-1;
[S,F,T] = spectrogram(B>window,noverlap,nfft,fs);
imagesc(T,F,log10(abs(S)))
set(gca,'YDir','Normal')
xlabel('Time (ms)')
ylabel('Freq (kHz)')
```

Coding for Cross-correlation:

```
load test.txt;
A= test (:,2);
B=test (:,3);
A1=detrend (A); B1=detrend(B);
figure, plot (A1);
figure, plot (B1);
Fs=2e6;
t1 = (0:length(A1)-1)/Fs;
t2 = (0:length(B1)-1)/Fs;
figure, plot (t1,A1);
figure, plot (t2,B1);
subplot(2,1,1)
plot(t1,A1)
title('s_1')
subplot(2,1,2)
plot(t2,B1)
title('s_2')
[acor,lag] = xcorr(A1,B1);
[approximately,I] = max(abs(acor));
lagDiff = lag(I)
timeDiff = lagDiff/Fs

lagDiff =

    338
timeDiff =

    1.6900e-04
```

Coding for Triangulation source location:

```
rsen=7.5e-3;
x1=0e-3+rsen;y1=0e-3+rsen;x2=1000e-3-rsen;y2=0e-3+rsen;x3=500e-3-rsen;y3=1000e-3-
rsen;
D1=sqrt((x1-x2)^2+(y1-y2)^2);
D2=sqrt((x1-x3)^2+(y1-y3)^2);
D3=sqrt((x2-x3)^2+(y2-y3)^2);
c=2700;
t1(1)=-45e-6;
t2(1)=-40e-6;
t3(1)=-15e-6;
t1(2)=-20e-6;
t2(2)=-25e-6;
t3(2)=10e-6;
t1(3)=-35e-6;
t2(3)=-35e-6;
t3(3)=0e-6;
t1(4)=-25e-6;
t2(4)=-25e-6;
t3(4)=-10e-6;
t1(5)=-160e-6;
t2(5)=-160e-6;
t3(5)=-130e-6;
t1(6)=-40e-6;
t2(6)=-45e-6;
t3(6)=-5e-6;
t1(7)=-155e-6;
t2(7)=-150e-6;
t3(7)=-115e-6;
t1(8)=-30e-6;
t2(8)=-30e-6;
t3(8)=15e-6;
t1(9)=-155e-6;
t2(9)=-160e-6;
t3(9)=-115e-6;
t1(10)=-155e-6;
t2(10)=-150e-6;
t3(10)=-125e-6;
Xcal=[];Ycal=[];
for jj=1:10
dt1=t2(jj)-t1(jj);
dt2=t3(jj)-t1(jj);
```

```

dt3=t3(jj)-t2(jj);
del1=dt1*c;
del2=dt2*c;
del3=dt3*c;
theta1=atan((y2-y1)/(x2-x1));
theta3=atan((y3-y1)/(x3-x1));
i=0;
for theta=0:0.0001:pi/2+pi/6;
i=i+1;
d11=0.5*(D1^2-del1^2)/(del1+D1*cos(theta-theta1));
d12=0.5*(D2^2-del2^2)/(del2+D2*cos(theta3-theta));
Xs1(i)=x1+d11*cos(theta);
Ys1(i)=y1+d11*sin(theta);
Xs2(i)=x1+d12*cos(theta);
Ys2(i)=y1+d12*sin(theta);
error1(i)=abs(Xs1(i)-Xs2(i));
error2(i)=abs(Ys1(i)-Ys2(i));
error(i)=error1(i)+error2(i);
thetacalc(i)=theta;
end
[Y,j]=min(error);
Xcal=[Xcal;Xs1(j)];
Ycal=[Ycal;Ys1(j)];
end
figure
hold on;
scatter (Xcal,Ycal,'Bx');
scatter ([x1 x2 x3],[y1 y2 y3],'Ro');
SourceposX=[180e-3];
SourceposY=[270e-3];
scatter ([SourceposX],[ SourceposY],'K+');
title('Trilateration Source Location');
ylabel('Y Position (m)');
xlabel('X Position (m)');

```